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CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D2.1 - Profiling Methodological Foundations

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Authors: FRA-UAS, RedCross, SoC, NTUA

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Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL - Missing Children Europe (MCE)	Belgium
	The Smile of the Child (SoC)	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – (Child Focus)	Belgium
	Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS)	Greece
	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (FRA-UAS)	Germany
	SingularLogic ANONYMI ETAIREIA PLIROFORIAKON SYSTIMATON KAI EFARMOGON PLIROFORIKIS (SLG)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
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Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of ChildRescue WP2 – “Grassroot Collective Intelligence in the Missing Children Investigation”. Specifically, it showcases the work done for T2.1, “Behavioural and Activity Profiling of Missing Children”.

According to the DoA, the aim of this deliverable is to find an appropriate methodological approach to create behavioural and activity profiles of missing children in a timely and accurate manner, utilising assessments from trusted sources, such as social workers and psychologists or friends as well as family members, if available.

T2.1 will serve as a base for T2.2 “Multi-source Analytics for Missing Children Investigation” as it provides a selection of indicators needed by data analytics and the respective algorithms for the analysis of behavioural patterns and the estimation on potential locations of missing children. Further it also adds to T2.3 “Stakeholders Privacy and End-to-end Information Pseudo-anonymisation” by underlining the sensitivity of the data that needs to be collected in the context of the ChildRescue response to missing children, which will be further taken into consideration in the deliverable D2.3. In order to establish a successful profile of the missing child’s behaviour and activity, data such as the mental state or romantic involvements are vital. However, this data is highly sensitive and should be treated accordingly. T2.3 will develop technical strategies to handle the data that was indicated as crucial in T2.1 in the most risk-reducing manner.

T2.1 had a twofold character: Both the state of the art of research on missing children was incorporated, as well as the international insights of experts in the field, who were interviewed with regard to promising practices and important information. This was completed in order to scientifically establish important indicators, as well as the appropriate theoretical foundation for the methodological approach. A categorisation system for cases of missing children was established and appropriate theoretical foundations chosen that were confirmed by the information given in the interviews and established in the research analysis. The first interest was thus to establish the theoretical approaches to scientifically base the practical approach of creating behavioural profiles of the missing children. After that, the methodology was cemented by conducting interviews with experts in the field to confirm the indicators found in the research. The interviews were conducted with experts from Denmark, Germany, Greece, and the United Kingdom in order to establish an international perspective on the field.

Finally, the results from the interviews were compared to the initial selection of theories, which endorsed the classification of cases with the chosen system. Through this careful and thorough vetting process, indicators could be identified that will aid in the timely creation of a precise behavioural and activity profile of missing children and thus contribute to the overall aim of ChildRescue to recover missing children more efficiently.

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1 Introduction

ChildRescue is guided by the vision to reduce the primary time between the moment a child is reported missing and the one when it is found empowering citizens to act as social sensors, by developing an integrated methodology that will transform the way missing children investigations are currently held. In order to create the ChildRescue methodology, a better understanding of the importance of different information is needed that will be included in the child's case profile. This will be developed in D2.1. ChildRescue recognises two distinct cases that are considered under a common approach; that of handling a missing child emergency and that of discovery and identification of an unaccompanied migrant minor. However, in both cases, further categorisation is necessary to understand and appropriately respond to cases of missing children, as the motivation and outcome might differ greatly. Those categories are runaways, parental abductions, kidnapping by non-custodians, missing cases of unaccompanied minor refugees, as well as cases with an unknown reason and outcome. The central aim of the present deliverable D2.1 is to establish the current state-of-the-art of research on the processes and information needed to find missing children through creating meaningful profiles. Additionally, D2.1 centres on establishing appropriate social theories to base the practical work done in the ChildRescue project in order to establish a methodology for the indicators and features that should be chosen to create a complete and informative case profile.

Specifically, D2.1 proceeds with the aim to:

- Scope out different potential social theories in relation to missing children that might help to explain the different types of cases
- Establish state-of-the-art research knowledge by extensive literature review in the field of missing children and related issues
- Identify key characteristics to correctly categorize missing children cases and create suited profiles in order to inform the search process that needs to follow
- Identify key experts for all different categories of missing children through research and the snowball system to ensure that all relevant knowledge is being utilised to get a full picture of the current situation in missing children procedures in the partner countries
- Conduct expert interviews with different stakeholder groups to establish important indicators with a unified interview guideline for all partners in order to establish comparable results for the profiles of the children
- Choose most appropriate theories for different types of missing children cases after the analysis of the expert interviews to base the profiles on
- Analyse existing documents on risk assessment in NGOs in order to make use of existing best practices that can be implemented in ChildRescue
- Establish essential information for the development of algorithms in later stages of the project
- Draft an informed consent sheet for expert interviews in keeping up with the data protection regulations of the EU

D2.1 provides the theoretical underpinning of the platform and app as well as the research-based information criteria that are needed for a scientific base of the algorithms used in programming the app to more effectively find missing children. D2.1 thus serves as the basis for the practical

implementation of D2.2 and helps to establish a current analysis of the state-of-the-art knowledge available on missing children.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 2 explains the chosen theories and their applicability to the research on the topic of missing children, more specifically the activity theory as well as collective behaviour theory, which is specifically of interest in cases of unaccompanied minor refugees where the collective can influence individual decisions. Social network analysis as well as subcultural theory shall be included to enlighten the role of informal networks on runaway decision-making processes. Victimology as the theoretical approach to victimhood shall be utilised in the attempt to grasp kidnappings as well as the computational based theories, which form the link between the research and the procedures of programming algorithms.
- Sections 3-5 present the insights from the expert interviews conducted in Greece, Belgium and Germany. Section 3 showcases the results from interviews conducted by Smile of the Child, focussing on the proceedings of different members of their search units in order to illustrate the different steps that are necessary to develop a fully functional search procedure and to shed light onto the identification process of different cases of missing children.
- Section 4 introduces the group of unaccompanied minor refugees that comprise their own segment within missing children cases and utilises the expert knowledge of the Hellenic Red Cross on the topic in order to establish best practice examples and also identify crucial information for the progress in those cases.
- In section 5 different stakeholders in the field of missing children were interviewed in addition to the practice partners' contribution in parts 3 and 4. Objective of these interviews was to obtain a range of different perspectives of stakeholders such as child protective services, NGOs focussing on homeless youth living on the streets and the police.
- Finally, in section 6, the results from the research analysis as well as the interviews are aggregated. Crucial information for the identification of missing children cases and their resolution are listed and the corresponding social science theories brought into play in order to create meaningful profiles of the children.
- Annex I lists the references included in the present deliverable.

Thus, D2.1 can be perceived as both a prerequisite for and an addition to D2.2, as the information on indicators and the resulting profiles feed directly into the choice of algorithms and thus crucially influences the outcome of the project, namely the platform and app. The effect will become visible in the piloting and evaluation phase of the ChildRescue project.

As already drafted in D1.3, the workflow process will include a regular re-balance and re-evaluation of the chosen theories and an ongoing process of a state-of-the-art analysis of current research on the topic throughout the duration of the ChildRescue project. The work process is hence depicted in the following graphic:

Figure 1-1: Workflow Chart D2.1

Albeit steps 1-4 have already been finalised for the purpose of this deliverable, Figure 1-1 aids to illustrate the process of this work and also points out the need for further investigation through the interrelated effect of the theoretical or methodological framework and the literature review of current studies throughout the duration of the ChildRescue project.

2 Overview of Theoretical Concepts and their contribution to ChildRescue

In order to appropriately discuss the phenomenon of missing children in the face of different legal definitions in different European countries, it is vital to adhere to the differentiation of cases that was proposed by Missing Children Europe (MCE), which distinguishes between runaways, abductions by third persons, international parental abductions and missing unaccompanied migrant minors [1]. Additionally, there are the cases with an unknown outcome and categorisation, which cannot be determined, the so-called "Lost, injured or otherwise missing children" [1], who have gotten lost (e.g. little children at the seaside in summer) or hurt themselves and cannot be found immediately (e.g. accidents during sports activities, at youth camps, etc.), as well as children whose reason for disappearing has not yet been determined. For the purpose of T2.1 those cases will be disregarded as their distinguishing factor is their lack of information, which unfortunately makes a characterisation of the missing child and an approach that takes the circumstances of their disappearance into consideration impossible. Thus, the named four categories will be at the heart of the theoretical classification in order to react appropriately to each case. Within each of the categories, further differences might appear which can lead to a different outcome for the missing child and alter their predicted place of interest.

Runaways, for instance, were further divided into five different categories based on the circumstance of the going-away situation by Payne (1995) (cf. Table 2-1).

Table 2-1: Categories and characteristics of Runaways [2]

Category of 'Runaways'	Characteristics
Runaway	Leave willingly, spontaneous, loss of (self) control, mostly reported
Throwaway	Forced out of home by parents, leave unwillingly, mostly unreported
Pushaway	Forced out of home by circumstances, leave due to lack of alternative, sometimes unreported
Fallaway	Contact lost, possibly leave willingly or due to natural disaster/humanitarian crisis, sometimes unreported
Takeaway	Forcefully taken away, leave unwillingly, mostly reported

Runaways, who decide to disappear relatively spontaneous based on a loss of control, either by themselves or the legal guardians and a corresponding subjective feeling of being overwhelmed with immediate social pressure. Throwaways or rejected missing children, who are being forced out of their home by their parents or other legal guardians and thus do not leave by their own choice [2]. Most of those throwaway-cases will not be reported as a missing person case however, leaving the children unfortunately out of the reach of the ChildRescue project. Pushaways or people forced to go

missing, in the American literature also dubbed 'push-outs' refers to cases in which the social network of the missing person forced them to leave due to unbearable circumstances. While there is some commonality with the category of throwaways, the difference is that pushaways are not necessarily asked to leave, but can be pushed out solely by the circumstances of their home, such as sexual or physical abuse [2]. Fallaways, otherwise known as people who have lost contact, are mostly adults, but can also include children in situations of natural disasters, humanitarian crises or so-called 'drifters'. They are defined as relationships that fall away due to either the constant movement of a person or other outside-factors, like a loss of contact after a disaster or death. The last category summarises cases in which the behaviour is not actually the active running away of a person, but rather missing children person cases in which the people were taken by force, hence called takeaways or people forced out of contact [2]. The last category clearly overlaps with the set of abductions by strangers or parents drawn up by Missing Children Europe (MCE), but can be a helpful distinction in regard to the apparent intent of people. In order to draft the methodology of ChildRescue and find suitable theories to accompany the research, a close examination of different reasons for going missing – and thus the categories explained above – are important as the circumstances of going missing can determine the action taken by the missing child after the initial instance and the resulting danger of being alone. Spontaneous instances of going missing, as in cases of runaways, for example, can sometimes be linked to short-term absence from the home and thus carry a lower risk than throwaway or takeaway situations. However, this is not always the case and should not be assumed due to the categorisation of the case as a runaway.

In cases of non-parental abductions, different distinctions can be made, either by motive, distinguishing between premeditated kidnappings for sexual or other types of exploitation vs. spontaneous kidnappings due to opportunity and kidnappings of foetus or babies satisfying maternal feelings, or dividing by offender-victim relationship into abductions by a family member, acquaintance or stranger. It is noteworthy that the abductions by strangers are statistically least likely to appear and only accounted for 24% of the 1,214 cases analysed in the study [3]. In general, child abductions are the least likely scenario in missing children cases. Another possible distinction between cases is whether the child was found dead or alive, which is most prominently being utilised in the profiling of offender types in the US [4]. Fatal outcomes can be linked to demographic characteristics of the victims in the sense of a victimological analysis. Beasley et al.'s study (2009) has shown a prevalence of fatal outcomes with older children going missing, as well as being Caucasian in the US [4]. Warren et al. (2016) additionally found a higher risk of fatal outcomes for female kidnapping victims in the US [3]. Parental abductions, if classified as a missing persons case, which depends on national legislation with Germany for instance not regarding this as a missing persons case unless the whereabouts are utterly unknown [1], also have different motivations and can be triggered by different circumstances, such as a custody lawsuit by one parent of an international couple in divorce or the desire to force a child into marriage in another country. Depending on the circumstances of the abduction, the physical and mental danger for the child can vary.

Due to the stark differences in the circumstances and consequent behaviour of missing children in those different categories, it seems vital to mirror those in the choice of different theories that might have the highest potential to explain certain forms of missing children cases. Thus, the selected theories shall be applied to the different cases and are not always appropriate for all scenarios as alluded to in D1.3 (cf. Table 2-2). Runaway shall in this case include all five forms of runaway behaviour classified by Payne (1995) [2].

Table 2-2: Categories of missing children cases and theories

Categories of missing children cases and theories	
<i>Missing children case type</i>	<i>Theories (examples)</i>
Runaways	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Third-person abductions	Social Network Theory, Victimology
Parental Abductions	Activity Theory, Social Network Theory
Missing unaccompanied migrant minors	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Collective Behaviour Theory

Focussing on an efficient and quick recovery of the child ideally prerequisites knowledge on the type of case, which can be received through interviews with parents and friends of the missing child, which are already a part of the best practices in the field. After this first determination is made, the behaviour can be explained and predicted with a higher precision if the appropriate theories are utilised to advise the quest for the most essential information needed for those cases. The identification of indicators that can follow after a correct initial categorisation of the case, allow for a timely response and recovery of the child.

2.1 System theories

System theories analyse the environment of an individual to explain their behaviour and thus identify correlations between environment and person. In missing children cases, this is especially vital when the child has not been taken by another person and thus has retained a certain degree of agency, so can be classified in Payne's concept as either a runaway, throwaway or pushaway or a case of a missing unaccompanied migrant minor. In those cases, the environment of the child that has gone missing can hold important information about the location of the child as minors sometimes join pre-existing networks of other runaway youths. In the following, different theories that follow the paradigm of system theories are discussed in regard to their applicability to ChildRescue. In cases of parental abductions or kidnappings by strangers, where the children have limited, if any, agency, the system theories don't demonstrate a high degree of explanatory power as the behaviour of the child is controlled by someone else. However, in some cases, the social network analysis can still be a useful tool, especially if the adult in control is a central person in the network or is in touch with other key persons of the child.

2.1.1 Activity Theory

Activity Theory (AT) focusses the analysis of human behaviour on the correlation between individual and their natural environment. So it "takes into account cultural factors and developmental aspects of human mental life" [5]. Activity Theory was developed in Russia in the 1920s and 30s and tried to link human consciousness and their behaviour by looking at the way the consciousness of people is shaped by what they do and in change shapes their handling of other, unrelated situations [6]. The goal of AT then is to understand the mental capabilities of actors and to analyse the cultural and

technical aspects of human actions. However, this demands an understanding of the environment that influences the shaping of the conscious and thus the following, unconnected actions as man-made as the influential tools that are man-made too so that no single individual lives outside of the influence of others [6]. In the context of missing children cases, this suggests that pushaways are heavily influenced in their decision to leave by their conscious which has been shaped through their environment and runaways as well as throwaways and unaccompanied migrant minors will be influenced in their choice of (re-)location by the tools available to their conscious. One of the main motives in the decision making process of youth who have run away from home was their limited access to service providers or other key individuals in the past [7], thus alternative tools might not be available to those adolescents. Furthermore, various studies on the personality traits of runaway youth in comparison to non-runaways were conducted and found that runaway children are more comparable to 'maladjusted' than 'normal' children, and are also non-compliant with social control instances, generally avoidant of difficult situations and typically grow up in family environments with little cohesion [8]. Thus, the consciousness which has been shaped by the family environment seems to favour building personality traits that increase the likeliness of running away. Hence, it is really not a certain characteristic, but rather a learned way of behaving that influences that activity of the individual.

"While it is necessary to be very cautious about imputing personality types to categories of people, it may be that people with particular ways of dealing with social situations and life problems are more likely to react by running away. Feelings of lack of commitment, being out of control, being likely to respond by action rather than inaction, all seem likely possibilities. This set of characteristics will not apply to those who have been 'takenaway'" [2]. Consequently, the environment should be regarded as a major influence on points of interest of these children and activity theory can be utilised in explaining the running away behaviour by allowing for an explanation of contradictory behaviour: "AT also tries to trace the causes for problems in an activity system by exploring the contradicting/problematic relations between the elements in an activity system and the influence of these contradictions on the results of activity (outcome)" [8].

2.1.2 Collective Behaviour Theory

Collective behaviour analysis focusses on the behaviour of groups of more or less organised people, as found in crowds, subcultures or mass events. However, the level of organisation can vary depending on the sort of crowd, which create their own patterns of behaviour. "Action is first; but the effect of action is to create an action pattern. This action pattern, as may be observed in the crowd, is frequently extremely fragile and ephemeral, and may exist without any clearly defined organization. Permanence of the action pattern, however, is dependent upon the existence of structure, upon a division of labour, and upon some degree of specialization in the individuals who compose the group" [9]. At the core of collective behaviour theory is thus not the action of a single individual, but rather a group acting as an entity, much like the Occupy Wall Street movement, which was loosely organised through social media accounts and created specific action patterns [10]. In missing children cases, collective behaviour theory is relevant when it comes to behaviour exhibited after the original instance of going missing, especially in cases where children are homeless and live in loosely organised collectives on the street, which can occasionally lead to a division of labour. However, as the formation of such a collective takes time, these cases prerequisite a longer period of absence from home. Minors living on the street usually do not fall under Payne's category of runaways as their

decision is made gradually by establishing their network or collective and are not spontaneous, but are often not reported missing when staying away permanently as the parents fear sanctions or do not care [11]. Thus, in the context of ChildRescue the collective behaviour analysis has limited relevance and can only be applied to 'newcomers' in those collectives who have been reported missing.

2.1.3 Social Network Analysis

"A social network can be defined as an array of social relations among social actors (such as individuals, groups, associations, institutions, nations, and even blogs), or as a set of nodes linked by a social relationship or tie [12]. A relation is symbolized as a link or flow between these units. The number of possible relations is potentially infinite and the term 'relation' can have many different meanings: acquaintance, kinship, family, friendship, commercial exchange, physical connection, presence on a web-page in the form of a link to another page, and so on. SNA [Social Network Analysis] is the systematic investigation of patterned relations among actors at multiple levels of analysis. The multi-level perspective of conceptualization" [13]. The focus of the social network analysis is thus not on the single individual but rather on the relations to other people in their network and the resulting ties that influence the behaviour of the person more than their personal characteristics [13]. Due to the ever-changing and relational nature of social reality, decisions of individuals are influenced by a set of different factors that can be hard to locate. Going missing, which is usually defined from the standpoint of those left behind, is a good example for this, as it can be defined as not being where the social network expects one to be and to thus fail to comply with the 'normal' social reality of their network [2]. In practical terms, this means that the structure of the social network defines their reactions to a child going missing: a report will only be filed when said child is expected to come or be home and the speed in which the report is filed also depends on how explicit these expectations are. In the case of missing children, a child who is supposedly out to play with friends for a few hours will not be regarded as missing until it has failed to return after the time it was expected to show back up. Hence, being missed prerequisites functioning social relations, as the network will be the deciding factor that shapes the behavioural expectations of the children. The relations in the social network can furthermore very directly influence the child going missing, especially in cases of throwaways or pushaways, where the social network and the resulting environment of the child are the deciding factors. A social network analysis of the family structures can be fruitful in cases of missing children as there are often pre-existing relationship issues in the families that were identified as characteristic for runaways [2]. The instance of running away is then often triggered by an acute episode of familiar conflict, like a fight. Additionally, in cases of runaways, existing social networks can act as pull-factors which spontaneously sway the decision to leave the guardian's control. In contrast, children might also run towards their families instead of from them, if they are in the care of a foster home or institution and want to access their families, but are restricted from doing so [7].

In cases of unaccompanied migrant minors, social network analysis should both focus on relationships with other adolescents in transit as well as online social networks as studies have shown that new technologies, especially social media, are utilised by refugees to plan routes, seek shelters and legal or medical advice, but can also be used by different actors to track the behaviour and location of people and possibly threaten them [14]. However, even with the use of new technologies, human relations are still essential as 49% of respondents in Borkert et al.'s study (2018) relied on friends and

23% on other refugees to help search for information. Despite relying on facebook and whatsapp for information, the most important source of information on routes to travel remains people [14]. Social networks thus highly impact on the actions of missing people as they can initiate the instance of going away or also potentially prevent it. Furthermore, as especially youth connect with peers via social media and 99% of adolescents in Frith's study have reported to use social media on a weekly basis, an analysis of their online network structures can be helpful in identifying key persons and thus determining potential points of interests for youth, who move on their own account as "[s]ocial media is now a part of the way in which young people interact with each other and build relationships" [15]. While social media data has already been proven helpful in assessing risky health behaviour [16], it could certainly also be adopted for the analysis of the actions of missing persons.

2.1.4 Subcultural Theory

Subcultural theory, much like collective behaviour and network analysis, focusses on the individual only in the context of their system and aims to explain the behaviour of people by considering the specific set of norms and rules that apply in their subculture [17]. "Theoretical explanations of subcultures contain two main elements or ingredients. The first is an attempt to demonstrate that the distinctive content of the subculture answers to the distinctive needs or interests of its members. It involves identifying those needs or interests and showing how the subculture is peculiarly fitted to satisfy them. The other ingredient of explanation lies in the conditions of interaction – that is, in the availability and access to one another of people who have in common similar life conditions and, hence, similar needs or interests, so that they may freely associate with one another and elaborate common cultures. This availability is not just a matter of propinquity; it is also subject to social control". However, it should be noted that the membership to a subculture is not exclusive, but that individuals rather belong to a series of different social groups, which compete for the degree of participation of the individual. The degree to which the subculture influences the behaviour of the individual depends on the amount of dependence from that subculture [18]. Especially in families with low social cohesion, alternative subcultures such as peer groups that are competing for the participation of the individual can thus have a stronger effect on the behaviour of the child as there are little alternatives and the opportunity to gain resources such as affection, welfare and status will rather be found in other groups.

In relation to missing children cases, subcultural theory is a useful tool in addition to the social network analysis in understanding decision-making processes that lead to runaway behaviour. As discussed above, in some cases the decision to leave home is not made spontaneously, but rather develops gradually through contact with the subculture of street youth [11], which leads to the development of functioning networks in that subculture and an increasing subscription to their deviant values and norms, which makes leaving home seem like a desirable alternative. Subcultural theory can thus be used to explain runaway behaviour, but also be applied to missing unaccompanied migrant minors as they usually heavily rely on the experiences and the norms of peers and gate keepers within the subculture unaccompanied minor migrants. Subcultural theory is less applicable in situations where the children did not choose to leave or where to go after getting thrown out.

2.2 Victimology

Victimology as a discipline looks at characteristics of victims and should be viewed as a dynamic approach that connects social sciences with legal categories [19]. Victimology focusses on the frequency and reasons of victimisation of people, especially in regard to the offender-victim dynamic and socio-political reactions to victimisations. In regard to missing children, the issue is twofold: On the one hand there are clear-cut cases of victimisation through parental abductions or stranger kidnappings against the will of the children. On the other hand, there are numerous applications of victimisation that happen after the instance of going missing, when children were not actually taken, but have to navigate in the social situation of having left the home. "There is an undeniable connection between missing children and the issue of child exploitation. The threat of exposure to high-risk activities increases significantly the longer a child is missing. Children who go missing, run away, or are abducted are often exposed to or suffer:

- Sexual exploitation, trafficking in persons, and prostitution;
- Illegal/unsafe employment;
- Involvement in criminal activity, both as a victim and as a perpetrator;
- Deterioration of physical and emotional health;
- Lack of education;
- Substance misuse;
- Risk of physical and sexual assault; or
- In some circumstances, death" [20].

While a lack of education and a deterioration of health are not instances of classical victimisation, the risk for young people who are missing to be criminally victimised is increased as the systems of guardianship are diminished or possibly even non-existent. Additionally, if children are being exploited as labourers or in prostitution, this might offer crucial insights into their location or places of interest and thus increase the likelihood of finding the missing children. Although it is highly desirable to locate the missing child before they are being victimised, being familiar with patterns of exploitation at the home location of the child might thus be of advantage too.

Additionally, in cases of kidnappings by strangers or parental abductions, the analysis of offender-victim dynamics such as online or offline grooming of young girls by adults can offer insights into potential locations of the child as well. This can both be achieved by talking to peers and family members as well as analysing the public information on their social media profiles that might showcase an increased interest in the child's activities by specific adults. In order to fully analyse these dynamics, ChildRescue will implement both the practices of interviews with peers and families that have been identified as an efficient tool in pinpointing potential locations of the child by experts in the field as well as analyses of online data.

2.3 Computational Based Theories for Activity and Behaviour Analysis

2.3.1 Social network analysis/Sentiment Analysis

2.3.1.1 Theoretical Background

The theoretical background of Social Network Analysis (SNA) was thoroughly described in 2.1.3 section of this deliverable. In the present section, the process of Social Network Analysis and Sentiment Analysis (SA) from a technical viewpoint is analysed and presented.

Social Network Analysis takes place from information drawn from observation of both online - and physical - network human behaviour [21]. Social Network Analysis software performs both quantitative and/or qualitative analysis of social networks. Some network graph characteristics that Social Network Analysis tools compute, among others, are [22]:

- Connectivity (e.g. shortest path length, diameter and density)
- Clustering (e.g. local clustering, global clustering)
- Centrality (e.g. degree, closeness, betweenness, eigenvector centrality)

Generally, Social Network Analysis software consists of either packages based on graphical user interfaces (GUIs), or packages built for scripting/programming languages¹. While the GUI packages are easier to learn and more user-friendly, scripting tools are generally more powerful and customizable. The most popular software tools used for Social Network Analysis and/or Sentiment Analysis are presented below.

¹https://ipfs.io/ipfs/QmXoypizjW3WknFiJnKLwHCnL72vedxjQkDDP1mXWo6uco/wiki/Social_network_analysis_software.html

Table 2 1: Sentiment and Social Network Analysis Tools

Tool	Description	Link	Category
Gephi	Gephi is an open-source network analysis and visualization software package written in Java on the NetBeans platform. Gephi is a visualization and exploration software for all kinds of graphs and networks.	https://gephi.org	GUI Package
Pajek	Pajek is a program, for Windows, for analysis and visualization of large networks having some ten- or hundred- of thousands of vertices.	http://mrvar.fdv.uni-lj.si/pajek/	GUI Package
UCINet	UCINet is a software package for the analysis of social network data. It comes with the NetDraw network visualization tool.	https://sites.google.com/site/ucinetsoftware/home	GUI Package
GUESS	GUESS is an exploratory data analysis and visualization tool for graphs and networks. The system contains a domain-specific embedded language called Gython which supports the operators and syntactic sugar necessary for working on graph structures in an intuitive manner. GUESS also offers a visualization front end that supports the export of static images and dynamic movies.	http://graphexploration.cond.org/	GUI Package
ORA-LITE	ORA-LITE is a dynamic meta-network assessment and analysis tool developed by CASOS at Carnegie Mellon. It contains hundreds of social network, dynamic network metrics, trail metrics, procedures for grouping nodes, identifying local patterns, comparing and contrasting networks, groups, and individuals from a dynamic meta-network perspective.	http://www.casos.cs.cmu.edu/projects/ora/	GUI Package
Cytoscape	Cytoscape is an open source bioinformatics software platform for	http://manual.cytoscape.org/en/stable/Network_An	GUI Package

	visualizing molecular interaction networks and integrating with gene expression profiles and other state data. Additional features are available as plugins.	alyzer.html	
NodeXL	NodeXL Basic and NodeXL Pro are add-ins for Microsoft Excel that support social network and content analysis. NodeXL Basic is available freely and openly to all.	https://www.smrfoundation.org/nodexl/	GUI Package
SocNetV	Social Network Visualizer (SocNetV) is a cross-platform, user-friendly free software application for social network analysis and visualization.	http://socnetv.org/	GUI Package
Meerkat	Meerkat is an automated Social Network Analysis (SNA) tool used to analyze, visualize and interpret large or complex networks of information, allowing users to examine patterns and investigate relational dynamics.	https://www.amii.ca/meerkat/	GUI Package
muxViz	The Multilayer Analysis And Visualization Platform, MuxViz is a framework for the multilayer analysis and visualization of networks. It allows an interactive visualization and exploration of multilayer networks, i.e., graphs where nodes exhibit multiple relationships simultaneously.	http://muxviz.net/	GUI Package & Scripting Tool
Netminer	NetMiner is an premium software tool for Exploratory Analysis and Visualization of Network Data. NetMiner allows you to explore your network data visually and interactively and helps you to detect underlying patterns and structures of the network.	www.netminer.com	GUI Package & Scripting Tool
GraphX	GraphX is the new (alpha) Spark API for graphs (e.g., Web-Graphs and Social Networks) and graph-parallel computation (e.g., PageRank and Collaborative Filtering).	https://spark.apache.org/graphx/	Scripting Tool

Oracle PGX	PGX is a toolkit for graph analysis - both running algorithms such as PageRank against graphs, and performing SQL-like pattern-matching against graphs, using the results of algorithmic analysis. Algorithms are parallelized for extreme performance. The PGX toolkit includes both a single-node in-memory engine, and a distributed engine for extremely large graphs.	https://www.oracle.com/technetwork/oracle-labs/parallel-graph-analytix/overview/index.html	Scripting Tool
STATNET	Statnet is a suite of software packages for network analysis that implement recent advances in the statistical modelling of networks. The analytic framework is based on Exponential family Random Graph Models (ergm). Statnet provides a comprehensive framework for ergm-based network modelling, including tools for model estimation, model evaluation, model-based network simulation, and network visualization. This broad functionality is powered by a central Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) algorithm.	http://www.statnet.org/	Scripting Tool
IGRAPH	IGRAPH is a collection of network analysis tools with the emphasis on efficiency, portability and ease of use. igraph is open source and free. igraph can be programmed in R, Python and C/C++.	http://igraph.org/	Scripting Tool
NetworkX	NetworkX is a Python package for the creation, manipulation, and study of the structure, dynamics, and functions of complex networks.	https://networkx.github.io	Scripting Tool
Tulip	Tulip is an information visualization framework dedicated to the analysis and visualization of relational data. Tulip aims to provide the developer with a complete library, supporting the design of interactive information visualization applications for relational data that can be tailored to the problems he or she is addressing.	http://tulip.labri.fr/TulipDrupal/	Scripting Tool

JUNG	JUNG — the Java Universal Network/Graph Framework—is a software library that provides a common and extendible language for the modelling, analysis, and visualization of data that can be represented as a graph or network. It is written in Java, which allows JUNG-based applications to make use of the extensive built-in capabilities of the Java API, as well as those of other existing third-party Java libraries.	http://jung.sourceforge.net/	Scripting Tool
sigma.js	Sigma is a JavaScript library dedicated to graph drawing. It makes easy to publish networks on Web pages, and allows developers to integrate network exploration in rich Web applications.	http://sigmajs.org/	Scripting Tool

The optimal decision on which Social Network Analysis tool should be used, depends on several variables, e.g. the development skills, the network's size, the focus on visualization or on computing network's metrics, etc. Although, in the general case, most of the packages are more difficult to learn than the privately maintained software, some of these open source packages are growing much faster in terms of functionality and features. Furthermore, for truly large networks (more than 1 million nodes), Pajek (from the GUI packages) and GraphX (from the scripting tools) are more appropriate to use.

In the ChildRescue's case, the question also lies firstly in the decision of the most appropriate tool that should be used. Of course, the pilot organisations' (SoC, REDCROSS, CF) available data must first be defined, which are expected to drive such decision.

Regarding Sentiment Analysis, it encapsulates the identification and extraction of subjective information and user-generated content from multiple sources to determine the emotions that are typically evoked to stakeholders and to elicit potentially hidden information about their profile. Sentiment Analysis focuses on emotion recognition [23], where emotions can be analysed and categorised in many different ways, like the ones which Plutchik created in the "wheel of emotions" [24] shown in figure 1.

Figure 2-1: Plutchik's wheel of emotions [24]

With the rise of social media such as blogs and social networks, interest in Sentiment Analysis has been greatly increased. Online opinion has turned into a kind of virtual currency [25]. Reviews, ratings, recommendations, and other forms of online expression are very useful for businesses to understand and cover the customers' needs.

7 popular commercial Sentiment Analysis solutions and 14 free popular platforms, tools and APIs that offer text mining, computational linguistics, clustering, Natural Language Processing (NLP), topic and information extraction are presented below respectively.

Table 2 2: Text mining tools

Tool	Description	Link	Category
SAS Text Analytics (Text Miner)	Analyses text data from the web, comment fields, books and other text sources	http://www.sas.com/en_us/software/analytics/text-miner.html	Commercial solutions
Lexalytics Semantria	Applies text and SENTIMENT ANALYSIS to tweets, Facebook posts, surveys, reviews or enterprise content	https://www.lexalytics.com/	Commercial solutions
Lexalytics Salience Engine	Is an on premise, multi-lingual text analysis engine	http://www.lexalytics.com/technical-info/salience-engine	Commercial solutions
Provalis Research (WORDSTAT)	Is a flexible and easy-to-use text analysis software – whether text mining tools are needed for fast extraction of themes and trends, or careful and precise measurement with state-of-the-art quantitative content analysis tools	https://provalisresearch.com/products/content-analysis-software/	Commercial solutions
Pingar	Is able to point the trends, topics and issues exposed in documents, posts, articles and emails	http://pingar.com/content-intelligence-2/	Commercial solutions
RapidMiner Studio	Is an agile platform for predictive business analytics.	https://rapidminer.com/products/studio/	Commercial solutions
Text2data	Conducts in-depth analysis of business unstructured data, and trend detection in social media data	http://text2data.org/	Commercial solutions
KH Coder	Is free software for content analysis, text mining or corpus linguistics	http://kncoder.net/en/	Free platforms, tools and

			APIs
GATE (General Architecture for Text Engineering)	Is a Java suite of tools used for many natural language processing tasks, including information extraction in many languages	https://gate.ac.uk/family	Free platforms, tools and APIs
R tm (Text Mining Package)	Offers functionality for managing text documents, abstracts the process of document manipulation and eases the usage of heterogeneous text formats	http://tm.r-forge.r-project.org/	Free platforms, tools and APIs
OpenNLP	Is a machine learning based toolkit for the processing of natural language text	https://opennlp.apache.org/	Free platforms, tools and APIs
KNIME	Integrates various components for machine learning and data mining through its modular data pipelining concept	https://www.knime.com/knime	Free platforms, tools and APIs
Orange Canvas	Is an open source machine learning and data mining software	http://orange.biolab.si/	Free platforms, tools and APIs
LingPipe	Is a tool kit for processing text using computational linguistics	http://alias-i.com/lingpipe/	Free platforms, tools and APIs
Apache UIMA	Enables applications to be decomposed into components	https://uima.apache.org/	Free platforms, tools and APIs

NLTK	Is a platform for building Python programs to work with human language data	http://www.nltk.org	Free platforms, tools and APIs
Scikit	Has simple and efficient tools for data mining and data analysis	http://scikit-learn.org/stable	Free platforms, tools and APIs
Scrapy	Is an application framework for crawling web sites and extracting structured data	http://scrapy.org	Free platforms, tools and APIs
Weka	Is a collection of machine learning algorithms for data mining tasks	http://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka	Free platforms, tools and APIs
CoreNLP	Is a set of natural language analysis tools which can take raw text input and give the base forms of words	https://stanfordnlp.github.io/CoreNLP/	Free platforms, tools and APIs

In the ChildRescue context, Sentiment Analysis will provide the means to gain deeper understanding of children's data and to create missing children's and unaccompanied minors' profile to try to predict their next moves or raise a flag when there is a "high-risk" of disappearance respectively.

2.3.1.2 *ChildRescue relevance*

As it is obvious, in Social Network Analysis the relationships are important [26], so the relationships might be the reason of a specific behaviour as well the result of it [27]. Thus, Social Network Analysis is extensively used in criminology. Social Network Analysis, Geographical Information Systems, Data Mining technologies are used for clustering crimes, finding links between crime and profiling offenders, identifying criminal networks, matching crimes and past cases, generating suspects, and predicting criminal activity [28]. It is also used to collect and structure information on criminal networks and analyse complex relationships involving criminal networks [29].

Additionally, except from the common social networks (before the digital era), there also exists another type of social networks, the online ones (emerging from Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc.),

where a large amount of data is created every second. Users are free to express their interests and opinions whenever and in any way they like. Through Social Network Analysis, recommendation and prediction of user behaviour is possible [30]. Some indicative metrics and useful information are²: friends (and their activities), likes, posts (and dates of posts), followers, actions on page, events, videos, pictures, stories, groups, use of emojis, messages. The data that are available in the web are from semi-structured to unstructured, so various approaches [31] exist such as clustering, face detection, user activities, content analysis and behavioural analysis to profile user(s) in online social networks. As [31] said, "Pattern recognition in behavioural analysis, type and number of activities in analysing the user activities are essential key terms in profiling the user(s) in any online social network."

Regarding ChildRescue, the above described Social Network Analysis & Sentiment Analysis tools could be used to find useful information about the missing child's personal profile. Some indicative example types of such information for the child could be the connections of the missing child, his/her social network, his/her activities, his/her hidden moods, any depressive or suicidal tendencies, influences, interests, etc. Furthermore, the comparison with past cases could reveal useful information, similarities, and differences that otherwise it wouldn't be feasible to find. In analogy to the use of Social Network Analysis and Sentiment Analysis tools in criminology to create a criminal's profile, ChildRescue aspires to exploit Social Network Analysis and Sentiment Analysis techniques and tools to create the children's profile, both in the general case and also from the viewpoint of victimology, in order to identify the profile and behaviour of a children, being a victim.

2.3.2 Machine learning methods for modelling human behaviour

2.3.2.1 Theoretical Background

The term Machine Learning (ML) was coined by Arthur Samuel in 1959 [32]. His definition about Machine Learning is that it is a "field of study that gives computers the ability to learn without being explicitly programmed"³. A more recent definition of Machine Learning given by Tom Mitchell [33] is the following: "A computer program is said to learn from experience E with respect to some class of tasks T and performance measure P, if its performance at tasks in T, as measured by P, improves with experience E".

Machine Learning is a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI) which is an umbrella term for any computer program that does something smart⁴. Generally, machines learn from and make predictions on data. Machine Learning has endless applications⁵ e.g. self-driving cars, virtual personal assistants (Siri, Alexa), social media services (people one may know, face recognition), email spam and malware filtering, product recommendations, etc. Concerning the deliverable's context, a review was made in the literature on Machine Learning methods about predicting human behaviour and personality traits.

² <https://sproutsocial.com/insights/social-media-metrics-that-matter/>

³ https://www.ibm.com/developerworks/community/blogs/jfp/entry/What_Is_Machine_Learning?lang=en

⁴ <https://skymind.ai/wiki/ai-vs-machine-learning-vs-deep-learning>

⁵ <https://medium.com/app-affairs/9-applications-of-machine-learning-from-day-to-day-life-112a47a429d0>

There are a lot of references in the literature about Machine Learning methods and its applications about modelling human behaviour. In this chapter some characteristic examples are described.

In psychology, there has been a great progress in tools that can predict personality traits using digital footprints such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram. Facebook allows researchers to record information [34] about users' demographic profiles (e.g., profile picture, age, gender, relationship status, place of origin, work, and education history), user-generated content (e.g., status updates, photos, videos), social network structure (e.g., list of friends and followers), and preferences and activities (e.g., group memberships, attended events). Moreover, user-generated text from messages, posts, or status updates can be further processed. Several studies have used Machine Learning to predict various personality characteristics. Most of them focus on the prediction of the "Big Five" personality traits of neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and conscientiousness.

Until today, Machine Learning approaches to personality assessment have focused on the relationships between social media and other digital records with established personality measures. For example, there have been some studies where users had also completed a Big Five self-report questionnaire. These studies showed that some variables (e.g. Facebook number of friends and favourite books, Twitter words per tweet and number of hashtags) are correlated with at least one of the Big Five traits, which then are used to predict users' personality traits [34].

Further personal attributes that can be extracted from the Facebook likes (which is a mechanism to express positive association with online content, such as photos, friends, status updates, Facebook pages of products, sports, musicians, books, restaurants) are the sexual orientation, ethnicity, religious and political views, personality traits, intelligence, satisfaction with life, use of addictive substances, parental separation, age, gender, relationship status, size and density of the friendship network [35]. The analysis conducted by Hartford et al. (2016) used data (Facebook likes, detailed demographic profiles, and the results of several psychometric tests) based on a sample of 58.000 volunteers obtained through the myPersonality⁶ Facebook application. The proposed model used dimensionality reduction for pre-processing the likes data, which then entered into logistic/linear regression to predict individual psychodemographic profiles. It achieved very high scores in predicting various personality traits.

Finally, predicting human behaviour in strategic settings using deep learning is another example. Deep learning (DL) is a subset of Machine Learning and it functions in a similar way⁷. If Machine Learning algorithms return a wrong prediction, then engineers need to make adjustments, but with Deep Learning algorithms they are able to decide on their own if their prediction is correct or not⁷. An example of a Deep Learning application is the prediction of the actions of human players in Go [36]. The approach of [37] evaluates Go board positions and 'policy networks' to select next moves. Deep neural networks are trained by a combination of human expert games (supervised learning), and games of self-play (reinforcement learning).

It needs to be noted though that, although machine learning has the potential to generate significant advantages above traditional assessment tools, machine learning personality assessment models are all initially validated on self-report questionnaires [34], so this is an important issue to be taken into account.

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/michalkosinski.com/mypersonality>

⁷ <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/machine-learning-and-deep-learning/>

2.3.2.2 *ChildRescue Relevance*

In ChildRescue, machine learning techniques are expected to be leveraged significantly to enable predictions for the missing children's potential locations, exploiting each child's case data gathered and also to enable common patterns recognition based on previous cases. However, no corresponding work could be identified through literature research on how to predict children's behaviour who e.g. ran away, using machine learning techniques. This could be seen both as an obstacle but also as an opportunity for ChildRescue. On the one hand, ChildRescue should deal with the fact that it should enter uncharted territories, but on the other hand it can be also seen as a promising challenge for the project, to open up new opportunities in research and science.

Currently, there exist many, different approaches for predicting users' individual preferences, attributes and behaviour to improve numerous services and products. ChildRescue will create analogies with and leverage such approaches to develop its methodology on the profiling part and the modelling and prediction of missing children's and/or unaccompanied minors' behaviour. Additionally, if there are enough data, case comparisons can be made with older, historical data to roughly predict the next moves of a missing child and/or to raise some flags in case there is a reason to believe that an unaccompanied minor presents a "high-risk" of disappearance.

2.3.3 **Descriptive Analytics**

2.3.3.1 *Theoretical Background*

Practitioners and researchers alike, find business intelligence and analytics an important area of study, as it allows the interpretation of the impact that data-related problems may have on modern business organisations [38]. In today's mainly data-driven organisations, the analysis of the data is crucial to their viability and can be of assistance in achieving their strategic goals.

In this section, an overview of descriptive analytics is going to be provided. Particularly, a short description of what comprises descriptive analytics and how they can be useful is going to be presented, along with some tools that can enable the analysis, and some challenges that need to be considered when employing them. Also, the bigger picture of business analytics, that descriptive analytics are a part of, is going to be briefly given. Finally, the relation of descriptive analytics with ChildRescue is going to be highlighted.

The main idea of descriptive analytics is that historical data are interpreted and presented in a tangible and easy to comprehend manner, so that they can be taken into consideration when future actions are estimated⁸. In all the aspects of management reporting, descriptive analytics are employed. Examples of descriptive analytics are the reports produced from companies that are an overview of the organisation's operations, sales, financials, customers or stakeholders⁹. Descriptive analytics is the way of incorporating lessons learnt, so it may be observed how past actions may affect future outcomes¹⁰. They are the conventional form of Business Intelligence and data analysis, and they provide a summary view of facts and figures in an understandable format¹¹. The two

⁸ <https://www.cornerstoneondemand.com/glossary/descriptive-analytics>

⁹ https://www.investopedia.com/terms/d/descriptive_statistics.asp

¹⁰ <https://www.cornerstoneondemand.com/glossary/descriptive-analytics>

¹¹ <https://halobi.com/blog/descriptive-predictive-and-prescriptive-analytics-explained/>

techniques employed in descriptive analytics are data mining and data aggregation. The most commonly used tools employed for descriptive analytics are given in the table below, along with a short description of how they can be utilised.

Table 2-3: The most widely employed tools for descriptive analytics

Tool ¹²	Description	Link
	R Programming is the leading analytics tool in the industry and widely used for statistics and data modelling.	https://www.r-project.org
	Tableau Public is a free software that connects any data source be it corporate Data Warehouse, Microsoft Excel or web-based data, and creates data visualizations, maps, dashboards etc. with real-time updates presenting on web.	https://www.tableau.com
	Python is an object-oriented scripting language which is easy to read, write, maintain and is a free open source tool.	https://www.python.org
	Sas is a programming environment and language for data manipulation and a leader in analytics.	https://www.sas.com/sk_sk/home.html
	Apache Spark is built on data science and its concept makes data science effortless. Spark is also popular for data pipelines and machine learning model's development.	https://spark.apache.org
	Excel is a basic, popular and widely used analytical tool almost in all industries. Excel becomes important when there is a requirement of analytics on the client's internal data.	https://www.microsoft.com/el-gr/
	RapidMiner is a powerful integrated data science platform developed by the same company that performs predictive analysis and other advanced analytics like data mining, text analytics, machine learning and visual analytics	https://rapidminer.com

¹² <https://www.proschoolonline.com/blog/top-10-data-analytics-tools/>

	without any programming.
	KNIME is leading open source, reporting, and integrated analytics tools that allows the analysis and modelling of data through visual programming. It integrates various components for data mining and machine learning via its modular data-pipelining concept. https://www.knime.com
	QlikView has many unique features like patented technology and has in-memory data processing, which executes the result very fast to the end users and stores the data in the report itself. https://www.qlik.com/us
	Splunk is a tool that analyzes and searches the machine-generated data. https://www.splunk.com

Of course, the usage of descriptive analytics is not a panacea and it comes together with some issues that need to be taken into consideration, while employing them. As the environment that organisations act within becomes more and more complex and competitive, making decisions only based on the insights of one manager or an individual decision maker is not sufficient [39]. The cultivation of a culture that enables taking into consideration the analysis of the data is required. Thus, the incorporation of descriptive analytics within the decision-making process entails all the challenges that are associated with changes in the organisation's culture. What is more, descriptive analytics mainly depend on the existence of historical data, as a result they cannot be significantly useful in new initiatives and innovations [39].

Descriptive analytics have also been accused of "killing creativity" and managers are required to find the balance between data-driven decisions and creativity or innovation [40]. Furthermore, as it is mentioned above descriptive analytics fall under the category of Business analytics. Business analytics is a term that can be defined as "a set of all the skills, technologies, applications and practices required for continuous iterative exploration and investigation of past business performance to gain insight and drive business planning"¹³. Business analytics comprise of: Descriptive analytics, Diagnostic analytics, Predictive analytics, and Prescriptive analytics, as presented in the figure below:

¹³ <https://www.slideshare.net/LightshipPartners/next-generation-business-analytics-presentation>

Figure 2-2: the 4 stages of Business Analytics

Descriptive analytics as explained above unravel what happened. Diagnostic analytics answer to the question of why something happened, with a focus of finding the roots of what caused a situation. Predictive analytics are employed to seek future actions and predict the potential outcomes of these actions. Prescriptive analytics have the aspect of finding the optimal course of future action, so that the objectives of an organisation can be achieved in the best way possible. In this step, usually decision analysis tools are also employed. In the figure below an interpretation¹⁴ of how the business analytics cycle operates is demonstrated:

Figure 2-3: The 4 stages of Business Analytics, Gartner's Model.

2.3.3.2 *ChildRescue Relevance*

For ChildRescue specifically, what is needed is to identify in the existing literature the methods, approaches, and techniques that can be employed to identify behavioural patterns, based on past cases of missing children or unaccompanied migrant minors, as they can be analysed by the existing records kept from those past cases. The analysis and discovery of behavioural patterns can be of assistance, specifically with regards to reducing the required time needed in locating missing children. Using descriptive analytics in order to build upon behavioural patterns is a research area that is still not widely developed. However, a specific area of studies that can be useful to look into for insights, on how to build these behavioural patterns by employing descriptive analytics is victimology.

The algorithms that aim at specifying and finding behavioural patterns in victimology use descriptive analytics. One of the ways that descriptive analytics are used is to narrow down who has the potential

¹⁴ https://www.gartner.com/technology/why_gartner.jsp

to be a victim and who has the potential to be an offender. In a similar manner and by adjusting the algorithms some behavioural patterns can be formulated for the children that go missing and for the ones that are responsible for them going missing. Of course, descriptive analytics cannot be used without caution, specifically regarding data that involve children and migrant minors.

3 Insights from the Hellenic Amber Alert

3.1 Development of an Interview template

At Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences an interview guideline was developed in cooperation with project partners and was utilised for all interviews conducted in the project in order to cover the same topics and generate comparable results from all international interviews. The template included a part on sociodemographic data of the interviewees for a better description of the sample as well as a narrative injunction on the organisational structures in working on missing children cases. Partners were asked for an aggregated 'case study' to depict the procedural steps and implications for the professional role of the interviewee. The interviewees were chosen based on a research on the major agencies or state stakeholders in the field and received an informed consent sheet for the interviews that included data privacy regulation as well as the procedure of the interview.

3.2 The Amber Alert Hellas

The **Amber Alert Hellas** is the National Coordinating Programme of timely and accurate notification of citizens on cases of missing /abducted minors.

"The Smile of the Child" activates Amber Alert Hellas upon the approval of the Greek Police Authorities.

The operation of the Amber Alert Hellas is based on the provision of quick, accurate and detailed information to citizens on a missing child case few minutes after the reporting of the case to the Police or the Organization "The Smile of the Child". To achieve this, a number of actors (public private, voluntary) are involved with purpose to communicate the details of the missing child and other basic information through the mass media (TV channels and radio spots), the social media (Facebook posts), SMS, announcements on airports' monitors etc. "The Smile of the Child" initiated the operation of Amber Alert Hellas in Greece in 2007.

The cases the Amber Alert Hellas is activated

In order for the Amber Alert Hellas to be activated, a missing child' case should be assessed and should meet some of the following criteria:

- Small age of child / children
- Clear indications that prove that the life or health of the child may be at risk.
- Suspicions that indicate a possible abduction or kidnapping of a child.
- The activation of the system will help to identify the child
- The activation of the system will not endanger the life of the child based on the police's assessment.

The objective of Amber Alert Hellas is to address the phenomena of missing or abducted children. The purpose is the rapid and accurate provision of information among the general public with regard to cases of missing or abducted children.

The rationale is the immediate public identification of a missing child within few minutes from the time that the authorities deem necessary the use of the program. The target group is the General

Public. Amber Alert Hellas is activated nationwide through the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000.

Figure 3-1: Amber Alert Hellas

Characteristics of Amber Alert Hellas

For the activation of the Amber Alert it is necessary to have the child's **photo**. The message includes the following information: Name, Surname, gender, age/date of birth, date & place of disappearance, psychical description (height & weight, clothes wearing when last seen, eye colour, hair colour, special characteristic etc.).

The geographic span of notification message is at national level and there is ability to withdraw messages upon deactivation of Amber Alert. The time span of notification message is 48 hours max.

Amber Alert is deactivated upon the location of the child or after 48 hours of activation. If necessary it may be reactivated again for another 48 hours.

Who receives the notifications and through which channels?

Tv and radio stations, social media, internet service providers, airports, public transport means, mobile telephone companies, electronic signs, volunteer partners etc.

Who collects the information from the public?

116000 European Hotline for Missing Children and Law Enforcement authorities.

How is relevant information channelled to the police officers that are handling the case?

Through 116000 Hotline the information is forwarded to the police authorities.

Which framework stipulates the cooperation among partners?

Protocols and memoranda of cooperation.

Registration to the AMBER ALERT HELLAS services in order to receive SMS

Citizens can participate in the rescue procedure of a missing child, by registering to the AMBER ALERT HELLAS, through their mobile phone. It applies for COSMOTE - VODAFONE - WIND subscribers.

More specifically, in order to register, the citizens only need to send the postal code of the area(s) in which they reside and/or work, and in the event of a missing child they will receive an SMS with the information and description of the missing child.

- The citizen sends an SMS to 116000 from the mobile phone with the postal codes they wish to use
- The interested person receives a reply SMS (without charge to the subscriber), which confirms the registration to the AMBER ALERT HELLAS service
- When the AMBER ALERT HELLAS service is activated, every registered subscriber receives a SMS with the information and description of the missing child (without charge to the subscriber)

Figure 3-2: Amber Alert General Architecture

In order to unsubscribe, the citizen has to send a SMS to 116000 from the mobile phone writing NO and is automatically deleted from the AMBER ALERT HELLAS service.

Today, 61 partners participate in the Amber Alert Hellas, part of the following different sectors, companies and organisations:

- Ministries and Public Sector
- Companies
- Internet Service Providers
- Mobile Telephone Companies & Telephone Operators
- Private Sponsors
- Media and Social Media
- Volunteering partners

Figure 3-3: Different partners participating in Amber Alert Hellas

Specifically, these are the 61 participating partners, per category:

MINISTRIES - PUBLIC SECTOR:

- General Secretary of Civil Protection
- Ministry of Order and Citizen Protection - Hellenic Police - Hellenic Fire Department
- Ministry of Shipping - Hellenic Coast Guard
- Ministry of Interior
- Ministry of Infrastructure, Transportation and Networks.
The monitors installed in public transportation vehicles display information on the missing child, as well as including posters of the missing child.
- Ministry of Foreign Affairs.

- Ministry of Justice, Transparency and Human Rights.
- Ministry of Health (National Health Operation Center)
- Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change.
- Ministry of Culture
- Ministry of National Defence
- Region of Attica
All the Electronic Variable Message Signs along the national highway, within and outside Attica, display information on the missing child.
- Region of Thessaloniki
All the Electronic Variable Message Signs along the national highway, display information on the missing child.
- Thessaloniki International Airport «Macedonia» - Civil Aviation Department.
Information on the missing child is announced throughout the airport, and all monitors show photographs of the child.
- Heraklion International Airport «Nikos Kazantzakis» - Civil Aviation Department
Information on the missing child is announced throughout the airport, and all monitors show photographs of the child.

TV STATIONS:

The TV programme is interrupted and a TV spot is shown with information on the missing child.

- ANTENNA GROUP
- MEGA
- ALPHA
- STAR
- SKAI
- MAD TV

RADIO STATIONS:

The radio programme is interrupted and a radio spot is broadcasted with information on the missing child.

- SKAI
- EASY RADIO
- RYTHMOS
- ALPHA 989
- ENERGY 88.6
- PEPPER
- MAD RADIO 106,2

INTERNET PROVIDERS & TELEPHONE (LANDLINE):

- COSMOTE
- CYTA
- FORTHNET

MOBILE PHONE COMPANIES:

All subscribers of mobile phone companies can register with the AMBER ALERT HELLAS service and receive information on missing children through SMS, when the AMBER ALERT HELLAS is activated.

- COSMOTE
- VODAFONE
- WIND

PRIVATE SECTOR / SUPERVISING BODIES:

- ATHENS INTERNATIONAL AIRPORT "ELEFThERIOS VENIZELOS".
Information on the missing child is announced throughout the airport, and all monitors show photographs of the child.
- Public Transport S.A. - STA.SYS.A (METRO-TRAM-ISAP)
- KTEL AITOLOAKARNANIAS A.E. through the monitors of the bus station
- ATTIKI ODOS S.A.
All Electronic Variable Message Signs along the tunnel, display information on the missing child.
- OPERATING BODY FOR UNDERSEA TUNNEL OF AKTIO - PREVEZA JOINT VENTURE OF TRIKA AEKTE G. MOUSTAFERIS & SON E.E.
All Electronic Variable Message Signs along the tunnel, display information on the missing child
- EGNATIA ODOS S.A.
All the Electronic Variable Message Signs along the tunnel, display information on the missing child
- ATHENS – ATTICA HOTEL ASSOCIATION
- HELLENIC CHAMBER OF HOTELS
- THESSALONIKI HOTELS ASSOCIATION
- AEGEAN AIRLINES
- GOODY'S
- TITAN CEMENT S.A.
- ACROPOLI TAXIS
- TNT EXPRESS GREECE
- NATIONAL BANK OF GREECE
- MOREAS S.A.
All Electronic Variable Message Signs along MOREAS S.A, display information on the missing child

VOLUNTARY BODIES:

- HELLENIC RESCUE TEAM
If AMBER ALERT HELLAS is active, then initially the local rescue team and gradually the national team will mobilize to locate the child
- RSF Hellas Group Communications and Volunteer Rescue
- CIVIL OLYMPIC VILLAGE PROTECTION
- Hellenic Red Cross - Volunteer Samaritans, Rescuers and lifeguards Corps
- VOLUNTEER ORGANISATION "THE SMILE OF THE CHILD"
- SEARCH AND RESCUE TEAM "THANASSIS MAKRIS"

3.3 Results of interviews

3.3.1 Interviews with Hotline operator

"The Smile of the Child" operates the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 since 2008. It operates the line 24 hours a day, 7 days a week and is toll free from both land lines and mobiles. It is staffed by social workers and psychologists (hotline operators/case managers). Its purpose is the prevention of the phenomenon of missing children, providing support to children who have gone missing and their families.

Its objectives include:

- co-operation with competent authorities
- providing support to searches for missing children
- providing counselling to the child and its family once the child returns safely at home

The Hotline offers its services to:

- Parents, children and citizens
- Police authorities for providing support in the search for missing children.

The Hotline deals with all categories of missing children:

- Runaways (National / International)
- Parental abductions
- Criminal abductions
- Missing unaccompanied migrant minors
- Lost, injured or otherwise missing children

The 116000 Hotline is particularly useful to children, parents and teachers who travel, since call receivers can refer callers to the competent authorities in those countries. 116000 Hotline provides a safety net for parents and children across Europe on holidays or for professional and other reasons.

The 116000 Hotline is interconnected with the European Emergency Number 112 of the Civil Protection Secretariat, is recognized as an Emergency Line, and is incorporated under Missing Children Europe (MCE).

The fact that the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 operates throughout Europe makes it a valuable tool also in the process of providing support to children arriving in Greece as refugees and migrants. This need led the Organization to establish a group of employees and volunteer interpreters / -mediators with knowledge of Arabic and Farsi. In addition, the line 116000 and related services provided were communicated through special brochures, at the points of entry and residence of children refugees and migrants in Greece.

On the institutional level the Hotline cooperates with:

- Ministry of Public Order & Citizens' Protection
- Ministry of Shipping and the Aegean
- Prosecution
- Children's Hospitals
- NGOs
- Volunteer Partners, including Hellenic Rescue Team, RSF Hellas Group Communication and Volunteer Rescue, Civil Olympic Village Protection, Hellenic Red Cross-Volunteer Samaritans, Rescuers and lifeguards Corps.

The particular services that the Hotline offers include:

- Assistance and consultation with law enforcement
- Activation of AMBER Alert Hellas
- Activation of the Search and Rescue Team "Thanasis Makris"
- Psychological Support to family
- Communication with mass media through radio, television and print
- Publication of photograph and information on our site (www.hamogelo.gr), on our social media and on the GMCN site (www.missingkids.com)
- Creation and distribution of posters in all publicly accessible areas

- Creation of photographic leaflets distributed through the Ministry of Citizen's Protection to all patrol cars in Greece
- Coordination of public and private agencies and businesses
- Psychological support and counselling of children once they have been found.
- Assistance and consultation in cross border cases

The following tools are at the disposal of the 116000 Hotline:

- AMBER ALERT Hellas
- IP Call Center of Cisco
- Contact Centre of Cisco that cooperates with the Siebel CRM application of Oracle
- ECAAS (European Child Alert Automated System)
- Search and Rescue Team "Thanasis Makris" with the active role of internationally recognized dog teams¹⁵
- Wide range of Logistics and Operational tools - Vehicles of Direct Intervention (jeeps, ATV, motorbikes, ambulances)
- The Mobile operational Unit of the Organization
- "Odysseas", a Mobile Crisis Management Unit

The Hotline of the Smile of the Child handles approximately 150 cases per year. According to the adopted cases classification, the following categories emerge: runaways, alarming disappearance, disappearance of unaccompanied minors and parental abduction.

Some statistics about the activities of the Hotline:

In 2015, 8.852 calls were made to the 116000 Hotline, and 141 cases of missing children were referred (69% runaways of teenagers, 13,5% alarming disappearances, 9% missing unaccompanied migrant minors, 8,5% parental abductions). Out of 126 cases that we finally handled, 119 minors were found (94,5%). Amber Alert Hellas was activated for 7 cases, while the "Thanasis Makris" Search and Rescue Team was activated in 5 cases.

In 2016, 10.065 calls were made to the 116000 Hotline, and 170 cases of missing children were referred (49,5% runaways of teenagers, 23,5% alarming disappearances, 14% missing unaccompanied migrant minors, 13% parental abductions). Out of 170 cases that we finally handled, 136 minors were found (80%). Amber Alert Hellas was activated for 9 cases, while the "Thanasis Makris" Search and Rescue Team was activated in 12 cases. Out of minors who are still missing, in 10 cases (6%) relevant communication was interrupted and in 24 (14%) there is an ongoing search (17 cases relate to unaccompanied minors and 1 was found at the start of the New Year).

In 2017, 9.379 calls were made to the 116000 Hotline, and 128 cases of missing children were referred (54,5% runaways of teenagers, 29,5% alarming disappearances, 4% Missing unaccompanied migrant minors, 12% parental abductions). Out of 128 cases that we finally handled, 105 minors were found (90%). Amber Alert Hellas was activated for 10 cases, while the "Thanasis

¹⁵ The Search and Rescue Team "Thanassis Makris" is staffed with volunteers specialized in search and rescue, while participatory dog teams are also staffed with volunteers certified in dog rescues, certified by the National Search and Rescue Dog Association (NSARDA) of the UK.

Makris" Search and Rescue Team was activated in 8 cases. Out of 13 minors who are still missing, in 10 cases (8%) relevant communication was interrupted and in 3 (2%) there is an ongoing search (cases relate to unaccompanied minors).

When asking about the existing practice when searching for missing children in Greece, although it can be considered to be satisfactory and effective enough, there is still room for improvement. More specifically, there is lack of information of the general public about the importance of informing timely the Hotline. In addition, there is a need for specific training of the personnel, which is involved in the search of a missing child, while it is necessary to raise the awareness of specific target groups such as teachers, parents, and students. Once the child is discovered, the procedure is as follows: it is necessary to have an official identification of the child by the police department. At this point, a clarification is required of the reason the child disappeared (was it a child abuse? etc.). Depending on the case, it may be compulsory for the prosecutor to be informed and follow the procedures foreseen. On behalf of the organisation, further support with high expertise is offered (counselling services etc.) It should be stressed that the main role of the hotline is to collect and convey information about the missing child to the authorities. The hotline does not substitute the role of police; it is supporting the authorities. There is collaboration with the authorities via MoUs with clear roles.

Some examples are presented below in order to understand the main elements of action and reaction when searching for a child.

Example of case 1:

On the 30th of November 2016 we received a call from a police officer informing us about the disappearance of a 17 year-old boy (unaccompanied minor) from a specific camp. On 24th of November 2016 he went to the Embassy for interview about his upcoming relocation. The interview finished at 16.30 and since then his whereabouts were unknown. He does not know the area; a friend of him escorted him to the embassy and then left. The missing child's report to the police was made by a psychologist of an organization responsible for the child. The child does not have relatives or other friends (apart from this one friend). The case manager started collecting information about the case and got in contact with hospitals (in case the child was transferred to a hospital), police and prosecutor. The case manager collected photos of the child and takes the approval from police and prosecutor for publicity. The information about the disappearance was disseminated via the Smile of the Child website, social media and mass media. We received a message by a citizen through Facebook informing us that s/he saw the child at a hospital. The hospital was contacted and the information verified. The police was informed in order to proceed with the identification. The public information on the child was removed and the public informed about the closure of the case.

Example of case 2:

Smile of the Child was informed by a social worker of an organization working with refugees about the disappearance of a 14 years old Afghan girl. She arrived in Greece with her mother on the 28th of February 2016 and they live at an apartment in the centre of Athens. The girl attends school (either via school bus or via metro). The previous day she started to go to school but she never arrived at school. She did not arrive at home at night and she does not have her asylum card with her. She is missing and she has not gotten in contact with anyone. The mother has reported the case to the police and has provided the girls' photo. The girl has a mobile phone on which she uses only viber. The girl is fluent in English and knows how to move in the Athens area via public transportation. Her mother speaks only Farsi. This is the first time that the girl has not returned home. Her classmates do not have any further information. The girl has a Facebook account. The case manager collects the information from the social worker and gets in contact with the police. The case manager continues to collect information from the mother too (the characteristics of the girl, family status, any other friends or relatives, pocket money, etc.). For any new information that the mother has not testified to the police, the case manager urges the mother to report it to the police and conveys the collected info to the police. The social worker informed us that the girl got in contact with a friend of hers via Facebook asking her if her mother is ok but then she blocked her and she cannot contact her again. The mother has provided her consent for the publishing of the photo and characteristics of the missing girl. The social worker informed us that the mother learned from a friend of the missing girl that she had announced her running away and that she would commit suicide because she cannot live without her father. This was reported by the missing girl 3 days before the disappearance. In addition, the mother found that her pills are missing. She was guided to report all the info to the police and we got in contact again with the police. With the informed consent of the mother and upon approval of the police, we proceeded with the public appeal of the missing girl. After the public appeal, we received a call from a social worker working at a camp in Northern Greece that she has seen this girl there. We talked with the staff of the camp, who also verified the information and we contacted the police to visit the camp for the official identification. The girl reported that she does not want to return, that she had committed 3 suicide attempts and that she had been beaten by her mother. We informed the prosecutor for the investigation of the case. The girl was transferred to a shelter.

Lastly, in the interview, the hotline operator was asked to evaluate the significance of some sources related to the investigation process (1 to 5, with 5 being the most important):

Social Media	5
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Parents/guardians testimonies	5
Friends/relatives testimonies	5
Anonymous tips	5
Past case of the same child (if existing)	5
Past similar cases	5
Transportation data (e.g. bus/train schedules)	4
Events data (e.g. big music event in the city)	2
Weather data	4
Criminal activity data of the area	5

3.3.2 Interviews with canine search unit member

“The Smile of the Child” has developed with valuable contribution of volunteers the “Thanasis Makris” Search and Rescue Team for missing children. The aim of this team is to conduct search and rescue in urban or non-urban environment to trace missing children. Key members of the Search and Rescue Team “Thanasis Makris” are international certified dog teams, while a Mobile Command Centre and several operational tools (jeeps, ATV, motor vehicle, ambulances) are also at the disposal of the team.

The team is in direct cooperation with the competent authorities to coordinate the search and in direct connection with the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000. All participants are trained and make all their resources and expertise available to the team as the main purpose is the immediate response and activation of all actors involved, as well as the optimal use of existing means to find a missing child. Key members of Missing Children Search and Rescue Team «Thanasis Makris» are the Canine Teams participating. The Canine Teams (handler and dog) are the only ones in Greece certified by the international NSARDA body (National Search and Rescue Dog Association UK) and the only Canine Teams in Greece, seeking a person. The Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children «Thanasis Makris» was created by «The Smile of the Child» in 2012.

- The Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children «Thanasis Makris» is activated once there is an extremely urgent case. Since, the Hotline considers essential the Team`s contribution, there is an exchange of information about the case and then the Team gets into action by offering the services and planning the actions accordingly. This takes place 5 – 10 times annually. The most frequent cases are missing minors who their lives are at risk independently of the category of disappearance. Consequently, the cases vary from runaways and abductions to lost, injured or otherwise missing children etc.
- The most critical step when missing a child is to immediately mobilise the rescue teams. The best practices in this field are mainly the immediate availability of the specialised volunteer rescuers

and the close cooperation with the respective authorities. The most important partners are the police department, the special unit of the fire brigade, Hellenic Coast Guard and local voluntary rescue teams.

- The biggest challenge to tackle during a missing case is *the time* since it is critical to discover the child as soon as possible and prevent any further implication to the condition of the child. The general public can be informed about the case via the activation of Amber Alert (to inform the general public) and via specialised volunteers that contribute to the search.
- The most important information needed is the age of the child, the health status (including mental or psychological issues), the family environment and finally the conditions under which the child disappeared (place and time of disappearance, timing of incident report). The most critical information that facilitates to great extent the recovery of the child is their personal smell in order to be 'utilised' by the K9 SAR Teams.

Lastly, the canine search unit member was asked to evaluate the significance of some sources related to the investigation process (1 to 5, with 5 being the most important):

Social Media	4
Parents/guardians testimonies	4
Friends/relatives testimonies	4
Anonymous tips	2
Past case of the same child (if existing)	4
Past similar cases	4
Transportation data (e.g. bus/train schedules)	3
Events data (e.g. big music event in the city)	2
Weather data	4
Criminal activity data of the area	3

3.3.3 Potentials for Improvement

The results from the interviews lead to some interesting outputs and outcomes about the methodology and the approaches followed when a child is missing. The most common cases are primarily runaways and then alarming disappearance, disappearance of unaccompanied minors, and parental abduction. Although, during the last five years, the runaways' cases were almost the 70% of the cases, there is an indicative increase of the alarming disappearances: 25% of cases (2017, 2016) and a slight decrease of runaways 50% of cases (2017, 2016). So, it would be interesting to examine

during next years whether this trend of the increase of alarming disappearance will be established or not.

During the first minutes of a case, it is possible to define what is the category of the missing child from the information collected. Each category is constituted by specific conditions. Once these conditions are known to the organisation, it is possible to define under which category the missing case is classified. Then, a specific approach is followed which is adjusted to the characteristics and the specific needs for each of the four cases. For all cases, it is a pre-requisite that the parents/guardians should report the case to the police in order to start the investigation.

Some basic information needed to classify the type of disappearance is:

Basic information about the missing child case

Information about the caller

- **Name and surname**
- **Contact details (address, telephone number, mobile phone number)**
- **What is the relationship with the child? (Guardian, relative, third person, etc.)**

Information about the missing child

- **Name and surname**
- **Date of birth (if not known, or age)**
- **Sex**
- **Origin and nationality**
- **Address, usually resident with:**
- **Language**
- **Disability (physical or mental), illness, medication**
- **Physical description: age, colour and length of hair, eye colour, height, weight, clothes wearing last seen especially physiognomic etc. characteristics (e.g. scars, glasses, etc.)**
- **School, class**
- **Mobile phone number, email address, Facebook account, twitter etc.**
- **A recent photo if it exists**

Information about parents

- **Name and surname**
- **Contact details (address, telephone number, mobile phone number)**
- **Marital status (marriage, cohabitation, divorce, dimension, disputes over guardianship child?)**

Information about the disappearance

- **Date, time and place of disappearance**
- **When and where was the child last seen and by whom? Was s/he alone?**
- **Has the child disappeared again in the past?**
- **What do you think might have happened to the child? Where do you think it may be? There is possibly abroad?**
- **Did something happen before the disappearance?**
- **Did the child disappear on his/her own? If not, who can it be?**
- **Have you reported the disappearance to the police? (Protocol number, police department that took over the case, contact details of the person responsible police officer on the case)**
- **Objects that the child has with him: identity, money, mobile phone (number), clothes, medicines, precious goods, other items.**

Among the above information, the most important information required is the age of the child, the family conditions (do parents exist? good/bad relation? violent parents? etc.) and the health status of the child. Sometimes, it is urgent to find the child immediately, since there are critical health issues that the child encounters (dialysis, missing dosage of medications etc.).

The most important information that offers *a better approach* of the missing child's case is the description of the child, the place of disappearance and the conditions under which the child disappeared.

The most important stakeholders that can contribute to the discovery of a child is the police department, the fire brigade, Hellenic coast guard, civil protections services, Hellenic red cross and volunteer teams.

Challenges

- ➔ The biggest challenge is that the parents or the authorities do not inform the organisation in a timely manner which causes a delay at the inception of the search. Thus, the most important element is to inform timely the Hotline about the missing case and then declare the missing child case (at police). In addition, the immediate collection of information about the conditions under which the child disappeared is highly important and finally the smooth cooperation with the responsible authorities is essential in order to examine, manage and cross-check the information received.
- ➔ There is a difficulty in the cooperation with the Authorities from times to times, while there is conceal of evidence on behalf of the parents in some occasions.
- ➔ Lack of clear responsibility and action from the stakeholders and actors involved in the care and protection of children.

- ➔ Lack of immediate mobilization from the authorities due to wrong assessment of the circumstances and motivations of the disappearance.
- ➔ Certified mechanisms and networks with expertise for the search of missing children are not utilized resulting in inactivity, lack of information or duplication of efforts in some cases.
- ➔ Lack of certified and well-trained professionals in the field to deal with the cases of missing children.
- ➔ For the case of unaccompanied minors, the lack of proper shelter areas and child protection facilities of good quality and care for these children increase the risk of repeated runaways.
- ➔ Low and almost inexistent reporting on the cases of missing refugee children due to a lack of awareness, knowledge and responsibility on who does what.

Best Practices

The most important element is the close cooperation with the authorities to exchange all necessary information for the trace of the child. Other factors:

- ➔ Timely provision of information on the disappearance
- ➔ Publicity appeals for the missing children without losing crucial time.
- ➔ Clear identification of the reasons of the disappearance
- ➔ Training of professionals involved
- ➔ Good coordination of the involved parties during the search and rescue actions in the field
- ➔ The ability to collect information from citizens anonymously and to convey them to the police (our Hotline can obtain information anonymously compared to the police)

3.4 Recommendations

Based on the results of analysis of old case studies of missing children, certain issues that need to be considered can be pointed out, such as:

- I1. The main reason for missing children is the bad relationship between the family members or with a girlfriend/boyfriend (these are the most common cases). The main characteristics of the missing children are that they usually are the most reactionary children while having the tension to get independent more quickly.
- I2. The living conditions of the child is the most important information related to the possible places of interest (e.g. is there domestic violence? etc.). Moreover, some useful information can be the hobbies of the child, a specific relation with other family members or a girlfriend/boyfriend, places where the child used to go, existence of summer family house and the extent of child`s engagement with social media.
- I3. Technology in the Amber Alert Hellas services: the organisation utilises on a daily basis Siebel CRM as well as the ECCAS platform, social media (for the announcement of the missing child; the presentation of the main characteristics of the child and the possible exchange of information with people that have an information that could lead to the discovery of the child), while data

analysis is conducted manually. On the other side, the rescue teams utilise mainly maps, SARtrack software, GPS and Copernicus.

- I4. Media are very important for the activation of Amber Alert and the exchange of information with the public that might offer useful information which will contribute to the discovery of the child.
- I5. The general public can be very useful in the process of finding a missing child. The activation of Amber Alert is the main tool of information of the general public. Moreover, bulk SMS is sent to the subscribers of the Organisation with the main purpose to offer dedicated information for each specific case.

4 Insights from the Hellenic Red Cross

4.1 Interviews with other international Red Cross organizations

Under international law, everyone has the right to know what happened to missing relatives and to communicate with members of their family from whom they have been separated. The main responsibility for ensuring that the rights of families who have become separated are respected lies with authorities.

Whenever people are separated by conflict, disaster and displacement or migration, everything possible must be done to establish their whereabouts, restore contact between them and if needed be reunited with them. Certain groups of people, such as unaccompanied migrant minors (UAM) and separated children, who find themselves separated from their parents as a result of armed violence, arrest, poverty, disasters and forced migration are among the most vulnerable and when in hosting societies in need of legal protection and alternative care.

4.1.1 Interview with the Danish Red Cross

The Danish Red Cross Asylum department has been running centres for unaccompanied minors for over 25 years. The number of centres has fluctuated in accordance with the numbers fleeing from conflict areas and poverty. At one point, the Red Cross was running eight centres, but there is only one centre left, namely reception centre Gribskov. However, Gribskov is closing too and the job of receiving unaccompanied minors will move to Denmark's main reception centre (for adults), where a protected section is being established for this job.

During this long specialisation, the job of receiving minors seeking asylum has been undertaken primarily at Gribskov (barring periods where the centre had other functions). The reception centre accommodated the minors for a period of 6-8 weeks (optimally), where after the children moved on to residential centres, some under the Red Cross flag and others run by local authority operators.

During the reception period, children experience a thorough and structured programme from the Red Cross including:

- Reception interview
- Introductory interview
- Health and medical screening
- Psychological screening
- Initial 'Life Skills' training
- Screening for trafficking
- TB screening (RC – health service)
- Information: asylum, rights, local and societal orientation
- Development plans constructed with the inclusion of the child and highlighting areas for their social, psychological and cognitive development

Additionally, case assessment by the immigration authorities starts during the reception period:

- ID interview
- Information and motivation interview
- Age assessment (not all)
- Asylum interview

Each child is appointed a primary care team of 2 contact persons. Their job is to assist the child in all aspects of everyday living at the centre, keep the child orientated on the coming schedule (the many appointments listed above) and, with the principles of self-help, support the child in navigating through a very difficult period of their lives – coping strategies. The centre staff tries to establish some continuity for the child: where do you come from, where are you now and where are you going, while focusing on the child's resources and competencies.

The Danish Red Cross asylum department does not keep statistics of the number of child disappearances. However, it is estimated that, approximately 60-70% of unaccompanied minors choose to 'move on' from the reception centres. There are different reasons for the high rate of children leaving the shelters, including, but not limited to: Denmark being a transit country for other Nordic destinations such as Sweden, Norway or Finland; their asylum application being rejected and their deportation being imminent; the nomadic socialisation of some groups of Northern African minors, who often return regularly to Denmark, using different names/identities. The Danish Red Cross mostly handles cases of unaccompanied minors seeking protection and nomadic groups, mainly North Africans, specifically from Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria, who live on the streets in the big cities of different European countries and survive through organised (street) crime and engaging with the system to get a little respite from street life. Occasionally young women (often of African descent), who have been picked up by the authorities in street prostitution or brothel environments of Copenhagen are also involved. With regard to unaccompanied minors who disappear, Danish Red Cross is powerless to intervene as it only has a documentation and orientation responsibility, which was identified as one of the biggest challenges in the work process of the Danish Red Cross.

In order to establish potential places of interests of the missing child, knowledge on the possible involvement of the child in street crime, an ongoing risk assessment including the testimonies of the practitioners working at the shelters and the knowledge of the location of other family members are essential. The criminal activity data of the area as well as the past case file of the child were identified as the most important sources of information for the search for missing children, which were rated with a 5 (the highest mark) on the scale.

Most important pieces of information to determine what kind of case it is (kidnapping, runaway etc.) were identified to be:

- Age
- Gender
- Nationality
- Context in which they are picked up e.g. at the border, on the street, raid on red light districts
- Mental state

In order to locate missing children, the following information is crucial:

- Knowledge of intended destination
- Time of disappearance
- Build-up of trust while they are residents at the centre: This contributes to our knowledge of the child, their motivation for being here, their intentions but most of all the building of relationships between the child and a primary adult. While respecting the child's right to privacy, anonymity and confidentiality, we also have a duty of care. Risk assessments are undertaken throughout the process.

- Time is a crucial issue, as many of these children have met unfriendly adults and authorities in their home country and/or during their flight. Trust takes time. That emphasises the necessity for trained professionals. Informing children of their rights and opportunities so they can make informed choices is essential but takes time to communicate adequately and appropriately.

4.1.2 Interview with the British Red Cross

'Surviving to Thriving' is a partnership project between the British Red Cross, the Refugee Council, and UpRising¹⁶. Based in Birmingham, Luton and Leeds, the project is enabling 500 young refugees and asylum seekers to become active and valued members of their communities through a range of support services and social action.

The project provides practical support to young refugees through helping them to develop life skills and offering advice and mental health support. The project also enables these young people to boost essential skills, such as leadership and employability, to ease integration into their new environments.

Additionally, the project works closely with several Local Authorities, building their capacity to deal with the specific needs of young refugees and to engage with - and learn from - their experiences.

The British Red Cross in the framework of the project offers one-to-one casework, dealing with the specific needs of young refugees; group sessions, designed to create social networks while increasing knowledge, skills and confidence; and help with access to services, including legal representation. Since July 2017 British Red Cross has directly supported just over 380 children and young people.

By experience, the main issues for children and young people going missing from care were due to concerns over being re-trafficked in the UK and then going into hiding when they have no immigration status and are terrified of being detained or removed from the UK. A big challenge is the lack of understanding amongst professionals about the vulnerabilities of unaccompanied children particularly to be re-trafficked and exploited. By experience, often social workers and police do not know what trafficking is, how to spot indicators or respond including not having heard of the NRM (process by which someone is recognised as a victim of trafficking in the UK). This means the crucial time period when trafficked children go into care the appropriate steps are not put in place to protect them which can contribute to increased risk of them going missing and returning to situations of exploitation.

Most important pieces of information to determine what kind of case it is (kidnapping, runaway etc.) are the following:

- Testimony of the missing child to their social worker, foster care, voluntary sector staff etc. before going missing
- Immigration status can be a relevant factor particularly if they have received a refusal on their asylum claim and are fearful of detention or removal (once over 18)
- Country of origin can be relevant and underlying risk factors or vulnerabilities as well as known history such as whether they were trafficked to the UK or have been exploited since arriving in the UK.

¹⁶ <https://www.redcross.org.uk/about-us/what-we-do/how-we-support-refugees/surviving-to-thriving>

4.1.3 Interview with the British Red Cross (second one)

The Young Refugee Service of British Red Cross works with unaccompanied refugees and asylum-seeking young people, aged 15-21, supporting them with the asylum process and the social care system, as they transition into the adulthood.

The Young Refugee Service offers support for young refugees in a few places in the UK – Birmingham, Glasgow, Hampshire, Kent, Leicester, Leeds, London and Luton. The British Red Cross has supported 110 UASC cases and handled 10 missing children cases during the last year. Most of the cases handled were categorised as runaways. In order to recover missing children, the process of understanding the child's motives for disappearing, identifying possible places of interest to the child, and contacting all stakeholders as well as the police and the social services are crucial. However, the limited time available to each case and the culture of disbelief in the Home Office were named as the biggest challenges in the effective and timely recovery of missing children. Children that go missing commonly suffer from trauma or mental health issues, have been removed or transferred from their accommodation against their own wishes, and have a marked mistrust of authorities. The social media accounts as well as the testimonies of parents or guardians were identified to be the most significant sources of information for the investigation process, both rated with the highest mark on the scale.

Depending on what services are available in each area, this could include help with understanding the asylum process, preparing documents, supporting children in health, education or social care crises, or informing the children about their possibility of getting support.

Most important pieces of information to determine what kind of case it is (kidnapping, runaway etc.) are the following:

- Case notes prior to child going missing e.g. Change of accommodation, any complaints from child, any relevant incidents.
- Mindset of child before went missing – provided by those working closely with them.
- Any history of trafficking
- Any indicators of trafficking

Important pieces of information to determine possible places of interest for the missing children:

- Social circles and networks
- Accommodation history
- Trafficking risk

4.2 Tools for transnational cooperation

The tracing request must come from the child and stem from a genuine Red Cross (RC) /Red Crescent Movement will not act upon Family Links (FL/RFL) Network is comprising the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and its delegations and the Tracing Services of the RC/RC National Societies around the world. The role of the FL Network is to restore and maintain contact between family members and clarify the fate of persons reported missing. The Central Tracing Agency (CTA) of the ICRC ensures coherence within the network and provides methodology and guidelines to Red Cross Red Crescent (RC/RC) National Societies (NS).

National Societies are called upon to play an important role as components of the international network for tracing and reuniting families and should have in place a consolidating a defective national network for carrying out family tracing and reunification. They must also draw public, humanitarian stakeholders and government attention to RFL services and their significance.

The Movement has long standing experience and extensive expertise in RFL. Through the FL Network it is possible to provide services across national borders in full transparency and with the consent of the authorities concerned.

A ten-year Strategy has been adopted to reinforce the FL Network¹⁷; improve quality and coherence, offer advanced tools and ensure that people and especially UM receive attention. This also means an improve of capacity to respond in, which is further advanced by the FL network. Emergency and migration are among the main areas of interest for the next RFL Strategy that is under development.

In the framework of the ten-year strategy 2008-2018 the Movement has developed new tools to enable increased capacity and coherence of RFL services across the FL network and also to increase outreach and accessibility to potential beneficiaries. At the same time efficient, effective and discreet treatment of cases on grounds of the Red Cross principles and the so-called 'Do no Harm' guide, which places the highest priority on obstructing further harm to the child, remain priority for all relative initiatives. In the following, different tools to aid the recovery of missing children/ children missing family members, will be portrayed:

1. The Family Links (FL) Answers

The FL Answers is a Microsoft Dynamics CRM/ web-based platform. The access to this secured platform is provided only to designated staff of the Red Cross Offices and a login and password is required. The platform enables the RC staff to register the personal information of enquirer and sought person as well as adding all tracing activities under specific filters and precisions.

2. Secure File Exchange

Secure File Exchange (SFE) is a secure platform to exchange protection related documents between and among Red Cross National Societies and the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC). Within the Family Links Network, SFE will be used for exchanging electronic documents related to RFL caseload that contain personal data

SFE enables the exchange of files by temporarily storing them in a secured platform that only designated recipients can download them within 30 days.

SFE is like an exclusive post office: as long as the recipient has an address recognized by the Post you can send letters or parcels of different shapes and sizes. Similarly, in SFE, the recipient must have an e-mail address recognized by SFE. Different types of documents of many different file types can be sent.

One individual user can send only one file to one individual recipient at a time.

3. Familylinks.icrc.org.

Family links website is dedicated to RFL and targets:

- a) Audience that are potential beneficiaries of RFL services

¹⁷ <https://www.icrc.org/eng/resources/documents/interview/family-links-interview-190309.htm>.

- b) Members of the FL network, in particular RFL practitioners, National Society, senior management, ICRC delegation management
- c) A further target audience includes humanitarian organizations and social services institutions that are in contact with potential beneficiaries.

With objectives:

- Potential beneficiaries receive accurate, appropriate and up to date information on RFL services and actors generally as well as specific contact information on how to access these services (National Societies and ICRC delegations).
- Beneficiaries can access online tracing services, and data can be shared in major emergencies within the Family Links Network and with external actors if appropriate.
- Awareness, understanding and appreciation of RFL services are enhanced amongst the public, members of the FL Network and other humanitarian actors.
- National Societies and ICRC are positioned better in RFL.
- Dialogue and exchange of experiences within the FL Network on service provision, promotion and capacity building is started.

4. Trace the Face and Trace the Face Back Office

In 2013 the Red Cross Movement launched an online tool called Trace the Face¹⁸, which aims to assist people to find their missing family members. The website allows people separated from their loved ones to upload a photo of themselves to advertise their search and increase their chances to be recognized. Those who wish to publish their photo online and take advantage of the Trace the Face tool should contact their nearest Red Cross/Red Crescent and ICRC office. To proceed with the publication of the photo in the website an employee of the Red Cross Office requests from the beneficiary to sign a consent form. The personal data will not be published without their written approval. The only information published is their photo and the nature of the family link to their missing relative; all other information, (name and location etc.) will be kept confidential. Once the Red Cross office receives the written consent the photo is uploaded online and if someone recognize the person from the published photo and wishes to restore contact with him/her they contact the Red Cross office through a form available for them on the website.

Trace the Face Back Office is only accessible to all National Societies Tracing Services. Only Red Cross/Red Crescent staff is eligible to upload photos on the Trace the Face Back office handling and registering the personal data both enquirer and sought person. Trace the Face Back Office contains also data about sought persons, to allow cross checks between different countries and potentially increase the chances of matches. To access the platform each employee of the Red Cross office needs a login and a password. To access the back office all you need is a computer/tablet/smartphone, a connection to internet and an internet browser. No need to install software. This secure platform is directly connected with the ICRC server based in Geneva. If a field trip in a non-connected area is foreseen, the RFL Officer can beforehand download and print the booklets of children and adults in a pdf version. The booklets containing the photos are available on the platform. Each National Society can see the National Societies consolidated case load of photos of minors and adults. Trace the Face Unaccompanied Minors (TTF UAM) is a restricted platform for the

¹⁸ www.tracetheface.org.

National Red Cross Societies Tracing Service in Europe to aggregate and share photos of minors and adults with the aim to show photos of UAM's to adults looking for minor relatives as well as to show photos of adults looking for minor relatives to UAM's.

5. Movement configured RFL tablets and e-registration are currently piloting and under development.

Tracing of / for UAM – Discussion

Tracing of individuals is possible after a relative tracing request (TR) submitted by a relative (the enquirer) and strictly on humanitarian grounds. The point of departure for the Movement to get involved in the tracing of families of UAMs is that this is a right that they are entitled to, both under the Geneva Convention and under the Convention on the Rights of the Child. While there is a clear obligation of State authorities to facilitate restoring family links and this is recognized in the legal instruments of the EU, this is by no means an obligation to be imposed on the persons concerned.

Therefore, a child cannot be forced to search his/her family, while there is the individual right of someone not wishing to trace a relative, as well as not to be traced (as in cases of UAM voluntary request of a state to initiate tracing activities, but will start from the starting point of a child's wish).

A person has the right not to be found; in such a case even if located his/her details should not be released without his/her consent. There must be clear procedures in place to respect information confidentiality by those involved in the procedures. A very clear system of gathering storing and sharing information must be set up. Tracing information is confidential information to the Movement. The child and the caregiver are the ones to be informed about the tracing results and they will need to decide if the information can/should be shared with other actors.

UAM RFL Basics:

- Respect to the wish of the child
- Respect of the data protection principles.

RFL Activities are often interconnected with psychological legal and material support for the families and persons affected resettlement or reintegration programs and social welfare services.

Protection needs of UAM

In great majority UAM are forced in migration. A forced migrant is a person who migrates to "escape persecution, conflict, repression, natural and human-made disasters, ecological degradation, or other situations that endanger their lives, freedom or livelihood"(IOM). Over the 50% of those forcibly displaced (51% in 2016 and 52% in 2017) were under 18 years old; by UNHCR estimations, out of them, the 75.000, in 2016 and the 138.700, in 2017 were unaccompanied and separated children (UASC), however it cannot be confirmed because they had been underreported. Coming from war torn countries and/or poor living conditions and being deprived of the protection of their family or supportive environment, UAM are exposed in high risk along the route and in host countries. There is a range of legal instruments in International and National Law indicating that children are entitled to legal and physical protection and assistance relevant to their age, gender and needs. The best interest of the child should in this regard, be the basic standard for all decisions and actions in support to the UAM in the EU. In 2017, over 30,000 refugee and migrant children arrived in Europe via the three Mediterranean routes. Of those, over 17,000 were unaccompanied. Dublin family reunion scheme and the EU relocation mechanism are not meeting the needs of unaccompanied and

separated children and their actual implementation is limited and slow, while due to migration law enforcement in 2016 they are often stranded in transit countries like Italy and Greece.

Figure 4-1: Situation update on UAM in Greece as of April 2018

Figure 4-2: UAM sought by the HRCTS in Greece in 2017

In Greece accommodation needs to exceed capacity. The safe zone remedy has been introduced by the International Organisation of Migration (IOM) in Hot Spots and camps and is implemented in cooperation to partners. Safe Zones are designated supervised spaces within accommodation sites which provide UAMC with 24/7 emergency protection and care (IOM and partners). In Open centers, children can leave voluntarily; thus it is difficult to keep track of children in facilities and places are limited.

A report released by UNICEF and REACH in June 2017 noted multiple difficulties faced by children following arrival in Europe, including lengthy waiting periods for asylum applications, age assessments, and guardianship transfers. In addition, those outside of reception facilities were exposed to specific risks, including cases of sexual exploitation, as well as limited access to alternative care in Greece. As a result, many children ended up being hosted either with adults or at emergency facilities. Many of these children have experienced terrible violence, sexual abuse, trafficking and emotional and psychological pressure not only during their journey but in Europe itself.

The case below is indicative of the complexities in regard to humanitarian needs of UAM and of the need of holistic multi-sectorial response:

A mother from Iraq, with two children, one of them facing severe health issues, was living in Greece. The mother left the country and reached Iceland. The children were left to a friend in Greece and the procedure for family reunification started. After a couple of months, the sick child left illegally from Greece and reunited with his mother in Iceland. The other child still lives in Greece waiting for the legal procedure to be completed having the support of NGOs among them the HRC Multifunctional Center (MFC). This case was communicated to the MFC Migrants Advice Bureau Service employee by the Icelandic Red Cross. The MFC offered information on the steps and legislation in Greece for the minors and an appointment with the friend and children was arranged, in order to address the needs of the children. After the sick child left from Greece, based on close communication with Icelandic Red Cross, the MFC followed up the case for the other child, which is waiting for the procedure to be finalized, in order to be reunited with its mother in Iceland.

Cases of unaccompanied minors that reside or have recently arrived in Athens visit the HRC Multifunctional Center for psychosocial support and legal information on how to reunite with their families. Most cases refer to teenagers aged from 15 to 17 that are alone in Greece with no relatives or a supportive network for them. These children have the right to be protected by the Greek authorities and have a legal guardian. However, long and complex procedures, as well as the difficulties they have already been through, make the children flee and leave the country, either to be reunited with their families faster or to find better conditions of living.

The best interest of the child, as enshrined in the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, must be the primary consideration of all decisions, actions, and programs intended for the protection of children. Adding to that, having all the necessary information for the child, but also offering accurate information to the child is the key to better manage each case and build a fruitful communication pathway with the child. Furthermore, sustainable collaboration and a good referrals network among relevant actors, sharing humanitarian values, is suggested as a best practice; such a network would be able in each case to address individual needs with compassion, however in a holistic professional and efficient way.

The Multifunctional Center for Refugees of the Hellenic Red Cross supports unaccompanied minors in various ways. Firstly, they are offered psychosocial support from the Social Service, where efforts to find suitable shelters, basic healthcare appointments and issuing necessary documentation for better addressing their needs are covered. Then, a discussion with the Migrant Advice Bureau Service takes place to be informed on the steps required either for family reunification or how to stay legally in

Greece, but also to complement the special characteristics of each case identified by the Social Service. Communication with other specialized actors follows for the certain case, aiming to find the best and complete solution to the problems the minor faces. Especially cases that have to do with family reunification include most of the times a connection of the MFC and the relevant Red Cross National Society, e.g. British Red Cross. Furthermore, the minor is informed about the children activities that are carried out in the MFC. As a result, the MFC of HRC offers a holistic approach, a package of services to the minor, aiming at offering a safety net for the minor.

4.3 Results of analysis of old case studies

4.3.1 Unaccompanied Minors in search for their relatives

Example of Case 1

Two underage brothers from Afghanistan appealed to the Tracing Service of the HRC to locate their mother who according to unverified information had also crossed to Europe. In the framework of the relevant interview conducted, the HRC Tracing Service assisted the children to go through the photos of people looking for their families uploaded on Trace the Face tool filtered by gender, age and nationality. The two boys recognized their mother among the photos and following the relative procedure the mother was confirmed to be in the UK where she had also initiated a tracing request with the British Red Cross. Currently the Red Cross network is assisting the family to maintain contact until they will be able to reunite.

Example of Case 2

A small Afghan boy living in a shelter on Samos Island placed a tracing request with the support of the local HRC RFL field officer for his mother and two siblings, a boy and a girl. The enquirer and his brother had been separated from their mother and sister on the Iraqi Turkish border. The two brothers reached Turkey together but were separated in order to travel to Greece on different boats. The second brother had finally been located in Switzerland where the two children reunited. The mother and their sister are still missing.

4.3.2 Unaccompanied Minors moving to other countries

Example of Case1

A mother from Afghanistan applied to the HRC Tracing Service to locate her son and her daughter who she believed they had arrived in the Netherlands. Following the relative tracing procedure it has been revealed that the two children had indeed arrived in the Netherlands where they were hosted for a while in a camp but they had left to unknown destination. By recent information they have moved to Germany, but this has not been confirmed yet.

Example of Case 2

A mother and her three children started the trip to Europe from Afghanistan, but they got separated to the borders between Iran and Turkey. The mother and the son arrived in Greece where they

stayed for a few years before trying to trace her daughters. Through Trace the Face Back Office where information and photos of the underage had been uploaded it was verified that they were in the Netherlands. In cooperation with the Netherlands Red Cross the HRC Tracing Service further facilitated family contact and exchange of useful documentation.

Tracing is possible across border to all countries of origin, transit countries along the migratory route and destination countries.

4.3.3 Unaccompanied Minors: victims of forced prostitution and trafficking

Example of case 1

The case of a minor from Syria, hosted in the HRC Safe Zone program in Ritsona camp applied for asylum in Greece on 10/05/2017 and the same day, he made a family reunification request with his brother who resides in Germany. His request was accepted by German authorities on 21/07/2017.

In accordance to Dublin III Regulation, the transfer should have taken place within 6 months of acceptance by the other Dublin country.

The minor was extremely anxious about his legal case and a lot of times he seemed to have lost his hope. The lawyer and the social worker of the program were in close contact with him in order to inform him constantly about the procedure, the expected time of waiting while they were in constant cooperation with the Transfer Department of Greek Dublin Unit.

The minor many times thought that he will never achieve to reach in Germany, and sometimes he felt forced of living in Greece.

Because of the prolonged procedure (more than 6 month) persuading the minor that his case is still valid and prevent him from leaving the shelter and try other ways onwards such as turn to smuggling networks involved a great support with regard to psychosocial support and legal advising.

Example of case 2

An UAM from Iraq, hosted in the HRC Safe Zone program in Ritsona camp, applied for asylum in Greece on 16/04/2018. His interview for examination of his international protection request will take place in the Greek Asylum Service on 22/5/2019. Due to his long term waiting until the asylum interview, he decided to move to Italy illegally without informing anyone, so as to live there with his uncle. He left Safe Zone and was arrested in a boat with other Iraqi citizens to Kerkira Island by local port authorities and was sent to Prosecutor's Office. The prosecutor decided not to prosecute the minor and to return to the safe zone. After his return, the lawyer, social worker and psychologist of the program supported the minor to understand the asylum procedure but also the consequences of his attempts to flee illegally. The social worker together with the lawyer still support the child in regards to receiving legal protection.

Example of Case 3

A 15 year-old Afghan was separated from his family in the borders with Turkey. He was staying at a shelter of an NGO that works with unaccompanied minors and had started the asylum procedure. A smuggler told him that he can take him to his family again, so the boy left. In Thessaloniki police

caught him and he was detained for 2 days, before coming back to Athens, where he sought advice and support from the Hellenic Red Cross Multifunctional Center of Social Support and Integration of Refugees (appointment with the Social Service for finding a shelter and with the Migrant Advice Bureau Service employee to put his papers in order, explaining documents and procedures, and arrange an appointment with a lawyer).

Overall discussion on examples of cases:

- Tracing requests from UM looking for their parents and from parents looking for UM can equally be the case; tracing is possible from Europe to other countries and the other way around, while there might be the need to search dispersed family members within Europe.
- Majority of the unaccompanied minors are considering Greece, as a transit country, an intermediate station, through which they will manage to reach to the country they dream of or the country where their family has moved /live.
- Pressure is put to unaccompanied minors from different directions. One of them is the lack of livelihoods in the country of origin that affect their families which might put extra pressure to the minors to continue their trip even using irregular networks.
- Finding the family does not always equal family reunification. Often there is need to help the family maintain contact after it is restored to avoid secondary separation.
- By interagency guiding principles, it is imperative to identify, register and document both unaccompanied and separated children as quickly as possible. Identification, registration and documentation are meant for the purpose of establishing the identity of the child, for protection and to facilitate tracing of their families. Priority should be given to unaccompanied and very young children. Even if immediate family reunification is not possible, tracing is important for restoring links with their families and so is re-establishing and maintaining contact between children and their families.
- If they manage to take a positive answer for family reunification, the lengthy bureaucratic procedures create to them anxiety, eagerness and disappointment which sometimes leads them to turn to irregular networks for facilitating their reunification with their families.
- The reasons for tracing UM should be purely humanitarian based on the do no harm principle, with the consent of the family or the legal guardian. In Greece there is a sensitive peculiarity in regard to legal guardianship.
- In all cases tracing should not violate the best interest of the child.

4.4 Potential for Improvements and Recommendations

Challenges

- Complexity of the environment, perplex, competing requirements and needs regarding child protection and tracing
- Humanitarian versus state tracing
- State driven tracing as part of the asylum procedure might lead to false enquiries
- Risks of the tracing been done against the best interest of the child, if there is no wish or informed concern of the child.

- Potential past abuse or harmful cultural practices in his or her family; well-founded fear of persecution of the family if child is traced
- Ineffective tracing if full informed consent is not given
- Registration of very young children

Issues to be considered

- Minors may have genuine well-founded fears, security risks, specific family issues that leads them to see that the opening of a tracing enquiry may place them or their family at risk
- Unaccompanied minors may not wish to return to their country of origin and might consider that the opening of an enquiry and a successful trace will inevitably lead to their return
- The appropriate profile of the person to have access to the UAM personal data

Recommendations

- Ensure all children on the move have access to comprehensive protection and humanitarian assistance, including psychosocial support, legal counsel, restoring family links (RFL), and information about rights and processes irrespective of their legal standing, age, gender or health status
- Recognition of the special vulnerabilities of unaccompanied minor migrants (UAM), the importance of avoiding detention of UAM and preventing and responding to GBV
- Facilitate accessibility to services that provide protection and humanitarian assistance
- The child is provided with timely explanation of all the legal procedures and appropriate information about their rights
- Put in place emergency reception and registration processes tailored to the needs of UASC.
- Take all necessary measures to identify UAM at the earliest possible stage, including at the border
- The protection to be strengthened through right registration and documentation process tailored to the minor's needs
- Use increased quality data and evidence to improve support for and monitoring of protection and humanitarian assistance to children on the move
- Priority for registration should be given to very young children, while the process should be gender sensitive, taking into consideration protection needs of both categories (very young and girls).
- Support RFL and Tracing processes through better coordination of protection, tracing, humanitarian services and the authorities
- Commitment to protect children and act only with their informed consent
- Share information with the child about tracing services and their potential
- Cultural mediation and translation to be used to remove barriers for accessing information and services

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- Constant need to distinguish between the humanitarian role and the different needs of the state; tracing is independent and neutral humanitarian service separable which stays clear of state's approaches or interests in the matter.
 - Family reunification should be the case only with the consent of both the child and the family
 - For all the actions taken regarding each case, the best interest of the child is the main principle
 - Mandate that all personnel working with children on the move undergo effective screening so they do not pose a threat to children and ensure they know how and where to make child protection referrals.
 - Build the capacity, through training and mentorship, of first responders to increase practical skills to protect children on the move

5 Insights from expert interviews in Germany

5.1 Results of interviews with German Agencies

Within Germany, different important stakeholders in the field of missing children and related topics were interviewed, including staff from child protective services, youth services specifically for unaccompanied minor migrants, non-governmental organisations working with vulnerable girls and street youth, police officers and researchers on the topic of online grooming or homelessness among minors. The sample included 6 different non-governmental and state organisations and the six interviewees were aged 33 to 62. All the interviewees hold a social science degree and those who were not in research had a work experience in the area of missing children that ranged between 7 and 41 years and were thus highly experienced experts on the topic. The interviewees were chosen to reflect a broad perspective of the manifold issue of missing children, but also to represent experts in their area. The mix of different stakeholders was chosen to enable a broad perspective on the issue that takes the knowledge of different actors into account to generate a comprehensive image of the most important sources of information.

Figure 5-1: Actors contributing in interviews

5.1.1 State Actors - German Youth Institutes (UAM; Runaways)

Two interviews were conducted with members of the German Youth Institutes, one of which works in German child protective services and one from the youth services. The interviewee from the child protective services is mainly in charge of runaway cases, while the representative of the youth services mostly deals with unaccompanied minor migrants. As state actors, the child protective services as well as youth services for unaccompanied migrant minors have custody of the children in their care. While every child has a specific appointed guardian, living in an institution leads to stricter rules on processes in case children go missing.

The first interview was undertaken with a staff member of the child protective services, whose department does not work in a foster care facility, but rather organises the cases in the institution itself. Thus, the interviewee is not involved in the search for missing children unless directly requested by the police in cases of potential trauma to the children. The second interview was conducted with a member of the youth services, who supervises the shelters for unaccompanied minor migrants and is thus involved directly in reporting unaccompanied minor migrants who are in the care of the state and aids more directly in the search process for missing unaccompanied migrant minors. The child protective services, in contrast, are not directly involved in the search for missing children unless the child contacts them or the police asks them to accompany them in case the child might be traumatised, but rather act as an intermediary between the child and the legal guardians after they have been recovered. The interviews with different state actors involved in handling missing children cases on different levels enlightened different aspects of relevance to the ChildRescue project as they both pointed out indicators for a classification of missing children cases in different areas and shed light on different procedures in the search for missing children.

The child protective services are especially involved in cases of runaways, which pose the majority of their case load with missing children, and, to a lesser degree, with cases of parental abductions or kidnappings by strangers. A crucial factor in deciding how to classify the case is the age of the child, as running away rarely occurs in young children, which fosters the suspicion of the child being taken rather than having left. If necessary, the child protective services will accompany the legal guardian to the police to file a missing person report. Another factor that was identified as being helpful in deciding if the child had run away was the timing of the incidence as many adolescents run away on the last day of school due to bad grades that they are afraid to show at home. While it was stressed that every case should be judged on an individual basis, the common theme that emerges in cases of children running away from home is the subjective feeling like the family situation is unbearable. This family situation can however differ vastly and spans from temporary, pubescent conflicts like not being allowed to stay out late for parties over difficult divorces that burden the child's mind up to physical and sexual abuse. The interviewee at the child protective services told that 1-2 incidents of missing children are reported to her per week, most of those are resolved quickly. Depending on the conflict, the resolutions and reactions of the child after the initial incidence of running away can also differ. In some cases, a reunification with the parental home is not desirable, especially when sexual or physical abuse has occurred in the past. In cases of parental abductions, the decision is especially complicated as it is not always apparent what serves the best interest of the child, which has to be the main priority. In any case, if a child has gone missing, the police will be alerted as they are the main state actor in the search for missing children with the authorisation to initiate search procedures.

Youth services for unaccompanied minor migrants are in charge of finding a suitable shelter for these children, which rarely involves foster families but rather state run youth shelters, which have strictly enforced rules and regulations. This leads to a more direct involvement in the search for missing children as they are the legal guardians of those missing children. The shelters enforce curfews for the children in their care, depending on the age of the child. Consequently, any teenager who misses their curfew by more than two hours will be reported to the police as a missing person. In cases involving younger children this procedure will be sped up accordingly. However, as approximately half of the teenagers miss their curfews by more than two hours, the active search will often not be initiated by the police until the next morning, unless it is a case of a high priority, such as young

children, a child with a disability or an unknown location (who cannot be placed at a party or other gathering by peers). If the teenager does not return by the next morning or the case has been declared high priority from the start, the staff members will interview peers, family members and staff members at other shelters or youth agencies the missing child might have been in contact with. They also search for the social media profiles of the missing child and analyse their content in search for clues to the location or activity of the child. If available, the current phone number of the missing child and its parents will also be utilised in the search for the child, although the new General Data Protection Law complicates this process. Data of current events, such as concerts in the area, as well as the case file of the child and the profile on dating apps were identified as the most important information sources in looking for the missing child, followed by transportation data such as timetables, interviews with family or legal guardians and social media accounts. The crime statistics of the area were deemed the least helpful. The risk of victimisation was estimated to be especially high for young girls who have gone missing after arranging a date utilizing a dating app. In comparison to Germany, Australia and the UK were named as positive examples of handling missing children cases, because the data protection law in Germany was viewed as too strict. Rather the child's welfare, both mental and physical, should be prioritized. However, some instances of children going missing are announced by the child prior to their disappearance. In cases of unaccompanied minor migrants this is often due to frustration about the lengthy bureaucratic process of obtaining legal citizenship or being allowed to proceed to the desired country of destination. Despite efforts of the shelters to stop the disappearance through measures such as taking away of passports, unaccompanied minors still leave regularly and put themselves at further risk of victimisation.

5.1.2 Specialised NGOs (homeless youth; street youth)

Two interviews with specialised NGOs were conducted. The first interview was conducted with a staff member of a NGO targeting homeless youth called 'OffStreet Kids'. The second interview was conducted with an employee of the NGO 'Zora', which focusses on girls and young women in difficult situations.

In Germany, street youth includes mostly children over the age of 15 who are mostly throwaways or pushaways. Runaways, who leave spontaneously after a fight, less frequently experience homelessness as they often return home after a relatively short period of time. There are various non-governmental organisations (NGOs) who target the children on the streets and provide services which are often anonymous. Due to the anonymity children who were reported missing are rarely recovered through these organisations as they are not identified as a missing person, but they do receive counselling on the issues that led to the incident of leaving the home. Consequently, they offer insights into the most extreme cases of children that are absent from home over long periods of time, despite not necessarily being reported as missing from their parents.

Children, who lived in institutions such as foster homes before going missing, are regularly reported to the police, whereas children who leave parental homes are underreported. The NGOs offer different services such as anonymous face-to-face and online counselling, parent-child mediation and support in family court cases. The most crucial information was identified as anything health related as issues in that area might need prompt solutions. Further issues identified were the existence of a warrant of arrest issued in the name of the child as that can also influence the behaviour of the child as they might go into hiding from authorities and are thus even less likely to seek help in case of their

victimisation. The most important source of information is the children themselves, who will only come forward if a foundation of trust can be established, thus an anonymous counselling is of vital importance to open possibilities of safe return from a life on the street for these children, which was stressed by both NGOs represented in this sample. The reasons for running away were located in the family situation and often involved mental overload on the side of the parents or physical and sexual abuse of the child at home.

The NGO named Zora specifically targets girls and young women and offers them possibilities to shower in and a second-hand closet for fresh clothes – thus, the organisation is exclusively open to women and does not allow access by males. The counselling covers many topics, ranging from issues at school, violence at home or romantic relationship over substance abuse, unwanted pregnancies to mental health problems and forced marriages – although counsellors recommend also specialised counselling centres, many of the girls who have been absent from home for a longer period of time and live on the street will not reappear at another counselling centre due to a lack of trust in unknown people. Depending on the age and the mental health status of the girls, shelter will be arranged, which will lead to a closing of missing person file if they are reported. However, less than 10 cases were identified as missing persons in 2017. Social media analysis and interviews with friends or family members were identified as the most important sources for information. Additionally, the experience and knowledge of street workers in the field of street youth were deemed vital, as they know where popular 'hang-outs' of these children are and can thus check them promptly. Ideally, the current phone number and the full name would be needed in the search for missing children.

5.1.3 Police (BKA/UK police)

During the course of this study, two interviews with members of different police forces were conducted. One interview was conducted with a police officer from the German federal police force called "Bundeskriminalamt" or BKA. The BKA police officer works in the taskforce on missing or unidentified deceased people ('vermisste und unidentifizierte Tote' or 'vermi/utot'). An additional interview was conducted with a member of the police force in the United Kingdom, who is in charge of implementing different software solutions in the work of the missing person taskforces in the UK. These software solutions can cause synergy effects with the ChildRescue objectives.

The police are the primary actor in charge of the recovery of missing person, who are in charge of overseeing the collaboration with other actors as well as execute the search missions. The German federal police (BKA), is in charge of co-ordinating international missing persons cases with the federal police forces in the other country involved in the case, but is not directly involved in the search process. The task of the BKA lies mostly in co-ordinating with foreign police officers to recover missing foreign minors within Germany or missing German minors in foreign countries. The United Kingdom, in turn, already implements specific software products in cases of missing persons that allow for geographical predictions of likely recovery sites based on past similar cases and that allow to contact missing persons in order to ensure their safety.

The BKA has a taskforce on missing and unidentified deceased people ("vermi/utot"), whose responsibility lies in aiding local police forces in cases involving foreign nations. This includes both cases of missing persons, who are German but went missing abroad and foreigners who went missing in Germany as well as unidentified bodies with presumed ties to other countries. Their involvement in

missing person cases contains missing children, including missing minor migrants and cases of runaways. If faced with minor runaways who are threatened by forced marriages, the police still have to inform the parents or other legal guardians of the recovery. In cases of unaccompanied minor migrants, the police force of the last known country of residency will be contacted by the BKA when the child or the bodily remains are found. Cases of (international) parental abductions, however, are not handled within the taskforce despite a missing person's report being issued for the child and parent. The cases are handled by the international legal aid instead. The vermi/utot taskforce of the BKA is informed by the local police force, which conducts the investigation into the cases, and receives all details gathered in standardized forms in the beginning of the investigations. The BKA taskforce in turn belongs to and cooperates with the Interpol affiliate in the other involved country, resulting in a differing quality of collaboration and response-time depending on the structure of the local Interpol office. This was identified as one of the major issues in the work process, as it can slow the recovery process down. However, the existing liaison officers were named as an example of a good practice to increase the speed of collaboration that should be broadened. The vermi/utot taskforce is thus mostly in charge of communicating with the local German police force and the foreign country's affiliate and acts as a mediator in between the two. They deal with few cases of third-person abductions but are heavily involved in youth who are threatened or victimised by forced marriages as well as runaways, who are romantically involved with a person in a different country or, recently, German youth joining ISIS. Thus, the group of minors who run away cannot be universally characterised as the reasons for running away vary greatly from problems at school over family conflicts to outsider-influence, such as romantic internet-relationships. The internet is used in the search process to identify key persons in the social network of the missing person through social media accounts as well as gather clues of potential locations of the missing child by reviewing places the child has been to in the past. The past case history of the minor, if available, was identified as the most helpful instrument to solve these cases, with statements from parents, friends and family members, past similar cases and flight schedules also being pointed out as vital, while bus and train schedules were named as the least helpful. Ideally, the person reporting a child missing should give indicators about their character, such as if the child is trusting toward strangers, potential locations or safe spaces of the minor in order to improve the search process.

In the United Kingdom police force, there are several different software solutions available which aid in missing person cases. The most widespread one is called COMPACT and has been in place since 2000. COMPACT started as a database for past cases of missing persons that was turned into a case management system that is used in 21 districts. The case management system eases the transition between different case workers as it collects essential information on the case and offers the option to create to-do-lists that highlight past actions and future tasks. Additionally, the iFind App was created for the police force, which can be used throughout the whole UK and aggregates data on past recovery locations of persons in similar cases, which can be used to inform the search process. It further offers statistical probability analyses of finding the missing person in a certain location based on the characteristics of the person. The App started on the basis of 1.500 analysed cases and improves over time as further use enriches its data base and resulting accuracy. The App was launched on the 22.08.2018 and is consequently still in the very early stages, making it impossible to predict its practical applicability or success rate. Additionally, Textsafe and Suicide Textsafe are utilised by the police to contact missing persons in order to reach people in need anonymously and ensure their physical and emotional safety if they decide to remain missing. The police force classify

missing person's cases into categories of 'high', 'medium', 'low' and 'no apparent' risk, which influences the further steps. In cases with no apparent risk, the police action is paused until a deadline, which leads to a review of the classification. Minors can also be classified as no apparent risk, leading to no police search for them in the beginning of the missing period. This can lead to dangerous situations for the missing child, especially if the police force is enticed to classify cases as no apparent risk due to their limited resources. The majority of cases handled by the police are runaways with a high percentage of repeat missing instances and an elevated number of children from care or hospitals who run away. The cases are classified on the basis of a risk assessment form, which include information on the character of the child such as whether running away is atypical to the character of the child, previous instances of going missing. Cases classified as high-risk can additionally be searched for with the aid of drones that are being sent to areas that are considered to be high-probability locations due to past similar cases and the statements of friends and family members. However, the classification is not based on one single item in the risk assessment but rather a triangulation of the aggregated data. In repeat cases of missing minors, the child protective services and the police will be involved in creating preventive strategies upon the recovery of the child in order to obstruct further instances of going missing. The most important information sources for missing children aged 12 to 18 were identified to be similar past cases as well as the risk assessment form. Ideally, a national database to compare recovery sites from similar past cases should be established to improve the search process in order to cover unusual cases as well, which can as of yet not necessarily be achieved by the relatively new iFind App.

5.1.4 Current research on related areas (paedophilia, homeless youth)

Two current research projects revolving around topics correlated to the aim of ChildRescue were also included in the sample of interviews to gain better insight into the data, in addition to including research reports in the literature review, namely MiKADO¹⁹ and the Streetyouth study in Germany by the German Youth Institute²⁰ (DJI).

Specifically, MiKADO (abuse of children: aetiology, darkfield, victims , *in German: Missbrauch von Kindern: Aetiologie, Dunkelfeld, Opfer*) is a study that was conducted over 3.5 years in Germany and Finland and was financed by the German Ministry of Family, Senior Citizens, Women and Youth. It was chosen due to its focus point on sexual misconduct towards children online and related grooming processes, which could potentially be helpful in identifying the location of a child that was targeted for offline sexual exploitation. The MiKADO project was organised in three sub-studies on sexual abuse of children, reasons for sexual interest in children and the darkfield of victims, which were all considered for this deliverable although the focus was placed on the darkfield as this study explored the internet as a danger for sexual abuse of children. The research project conducted a series of surveys with adults and children to include both perspectives. 28.000 adults completed the survey as well as over 2.000 minors. It aimed at developing preventive strategies to obstruct the further sexual abuse of children off- and online.

Additionally, the German Youth Institute (DJI) was included due to their study on the life situation of children on the streets of Germany, which was published in a comprehensive report on the different

¹⁹ <http://www.mikado-studie.de/index.php/101.htm>.

²⁰ www.dji.de/strassenjugendliche.

situations and needs of streetyouth in 2017. Prior to the publication of the report, the DJI had supervised four model projects and interviewed both the leaders of the model projects as well as youth participants. Additionally, 300 in-depth interviews with street youth under the age of 25 were conducted.

MiKado discovered that 97% of teenagers are online daily or multiple times a week, making the internet an important environment for children and placing crucial parts of their social networks online. However, this also makes them vulnerable to being approached inappropriately by adults and indeed approaching adults themselves. The choice of the individual child is dependent on the preferences of the adults who engage with the child. Adults will target children specifically by their preferred age and gender. Online communication is often explicit in nature before meeting offline does happen. Offline meetings occur in 25% of all cases in which the child only knows the adult from online interactions. The grooming process can vary in form and time. The analysis of private messages could theoretically be most informative as much of the sexual misconduct happens online, however publicly available data from social media apps, such as likes on photos, can already serve as an indicator for a close relationship with an adult.

The study conducted by the German Youth Institute, which focusses on adolescents living on the street supports the interview results from the NGOs. Children living on the streets, who are mostly teenagers, are usually 'de-coupled' from the system, meaning they no longer attend school or any other educational institution or work. They mostly sleep rough at times and 'couch-hop' at other instances. Girls especially often stay at older acquaintances homes, which put them at risk of sexual exploitation or abuse. Reasons for leaving their homes are mostly family issues ranging from abuse over neglect to mental health issues. Homeless youth often have irregular access to social media, but do make use of Facebook groups to gain access to help, which is critical due to data protection issues. Online counselling, as offered by many NGOs, is especially helpful for children who are couch-hopping and thus have access to a computer.

6 Methodology in creating children's behavioural profiles

6.1 Selection of Theories based on interview data

The interviews underlined the importance of the context of the disappearance of the child for the quick and successful resolution of the case. In accordance with the proposed differentiation by Missing Children Europe, T2.1 follows the classification into runaways, abductions by third persons, international parental abductions and missing unaccompanied migrant minors, with the addition of lost, injured or otherwise missing children for cases with an unknown outcome as explained in section 2. Due to the vastly different circumstances of these cases and the varying degrees of agency of the child involved, which can critically influence the success of a behaviour prediction, it seems sensible to utilise different theories and apply a risk assessment-tool, first in the process of gathering data on the individual case, which also establishes a probable link to one of the categories. After the initial categorisation, different information can be of specific importance for the creation of the behavioural profile of the child. For example, asking for the intended location, as identified in the interviews by the Hellenic Red Cross, seems vital for cases of runaways or unaccompanied minor migrants, but less so in cases of child abductions as the missing child will not necessarily be able to influence that choice.

Consequently, the choices of theoretical approaches that substantiate the practical response to the cases, cannot be unified, but rather depend on the individual case and its categorisation. All cases require a timely response that should be initiated through the risk assessment and followed up by a case-specific approach of uniting all existing knowledge on the missing child through interviews with family members and friends as well as a review of the existing casefile and an analysis of their social media profiles. The case specific approach then depends on the probable circumstances of the case. While a wrong categorisation can potentially include unnecessary information or lead to wrong behavioural predictions, the procedure also offers the possibility of a timelier response and a more efficient recovery of the child which can reduce their risk of victimisation. Thus, the proceeding explained in section 2 stands as valid. In cases of runaways, when the child has a relatively high amount of agency, the approach of analysing the social network of the child is most promising as it might reveal key persons or locations of interest to the child. Furthermore, utilising subcultural theory and the interview results with members of the NGOs working with street youth in Germany, it can be argued that so-called 'hotspots' for runaway children exist within the cities, which can be identified through the expertise of social workers, interviews with peers or existing case files on earlier recovery locations of the child. Additionally, Activity Theory can be applied to understand the behavioural patterns of the child within its environment. In cases of missing unaccompanied minors who left the shelters willingly, subcultural theory and activity theory can also be applied. Additionally, collective behaviour theory can be enlightening as the children live in shelters and both the interviews as well as the research have highlighted the importance of 'group intelligence', meaning the information that is passed through the trusted channels of other minor migrants, for the decision to relocate.

On the contrast, in cases with little agency on the child's side, such as parental abductions or third-person abductions, the prediction of the behaviour of the child based on their previous behaviour is more difficult and the implementation of algorithms focussing on the child's profile can be restrained in its effect. Yet, in cases of parental abductions, the location of the child might be revealed on its social media site and the social network theory can be applied more generally to identify key contact

persons for both the parent and the child such as other family members or new partners, which could be sources of information on or be identified as the location of the missing child. In cases of third-person abductions, an analysis of the social network of the child could reveal the perpetrator in cases where a child was specifically targeted. Thus, the proposed choice of theories from section 2 was further supported by the results of the interviews and should be applied after the initial risk assessment and categorisation of the individual case.

6.2 Indicators for algorithms

The indicators that could be utilised in data analytics are based on the results from both the interview data as well as best practices found in documents of the partners and the state-of-the-art research review that was conducted for ChildRescue.

Figure 6-1: Different sources contributing to the indicators of the profiles

Different indicators were identified, but the clear re-emerging theme was family conflicts and issues in the structures of the families (due to problematic divorces). This should thus be prioritised as children with challenging homes are also less likely to return and children involved in custody disputes could be located at their other parent's home. Adapting the profiling methods of the FBI used in the search for offenders [41] for a prediction of the behaviour of missing children, the following profiling characteristics emerge when disregarding all information related to criminal offending:

Basic information extracted from the FBI offender profiling

- Emotional state
- Socio economic standing
- Hobbies
- Lifestyle
- Social/sexual competence
- Age
- Gender
- Vehicle
- Place of residence (so far)
- Behaviour
- Norms and believes (cf. *ibid.*)

In the interviews conducted by Smile of the Child, the Hellenic Red Cross and the Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences, the following indicators were identified:

Smile of the Child	Hellenic Red Cross	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences
General info (Full name, gender, phone number, school, nationality, language)	General info (name, gender, nationality)	General info (full name, gender, phone number)
Age	Age	Age to determine likelihood of runaway vs. kidnapping
Family situation	Immigration status	Family situation
Health status (substance abuse, disease, emotional and mental state)	Health status (mental state)	Health status (substance abuse; disease; emotional and mental state)
Time the child was last seen	Time of disappearance	Timing
Key persons (family, friends, others)	Context of recovery site (red-light district, border ...)	Access to dating apps
Location the child was last seen	Intended location	Police warrant

Table 6-1: Different indicators named in the interviews

This overlaps partly with the findings from the literature review, namely:

Indicators in research literature

- Family structures ([2], [11], [42] / Family situation (divorce, pubescent conflict, physical/ mental/ sexual abuse, neglect, substance abuse)
- Risk of socioeconomic status [7]
- Substance abuse
- Age (to know if child ran away or was taken)
- Timing (last day of school)
- Announced leaving (unaccompanied minor migrants)
- Emotional/mental state (risk of suicide or harm of others)
- Limited access to alternative help resources/ forced restraint from seeing family or friends [7]

6.3 Challenges in creating profiles of missing children

The biggest challenge that ChildRescue will face when creating the profiles of missing children is the lack of or false information delivered by parents and friends. In order to correctly predict the behavioural pattern of the child and for ChildRescue to minimise the time of the recovery of the child, the necessary information needs to be available and correct. In some cases, this can prove to be challenging. This is especially true in cases of unaccompanied minor migrants who have not spend a long time in their shelter before going missing and thus do not have close friends who could give a testimony and the parents are not reachable due to a lack of contact information or unwillingness to cooperate. In these cases, the initial categorisation might be difficult as it could both be runaway or kidnapping cases.

Furthermore, if key contact persons cannot be reached, the timeliness of the response of ChildRescue is limited as it requires the initial assessment through the child's profile. Additionally, the complete lack of trustworthy information can hinder the successful creation of a profile, which renders a prediction of their behaviour very challenging to almost impossible. The same issue can be faced in cases of missing children with uncooperative parents and friends, who do not comply with the protocol of filling in the information sheet. Additionally, friends of runaways, who are teenagers themselves, might feel like they betray their friends if they volunteer information on their whereabouts, if the missing child does not want to be found, resulting in a lack of trustworthiness of given information.

Also, due to the different nature of the relationship with parents and friends and the resulting different behaviour of the child in the interaction with these different actor groups, the testimony of the friends and the parents can differ greatly in relation to the character and behaviour of the child. This can make the correct prediction of behavioural patterns of the child more difficult. In cases of kidnappings the behaviour of the child is only relevant if there was online grooming of the perpetrator on the child's social media profiles as it may point to the location of the child.

In cases of spontaneous kidnappings of children due to an opportunity to take an unsupervised child, the profiles based on the child's behaviour unfortunately won't be successful in aiding the recovery.

Still, in cases in which the child has some degree of agency, the methodology of creating profiles of the children based on their characteristics and behavioural patterns can be applied successfully, rendering the approach of ChildRescue especially helpful in cases of runaways, which also make up the majority of the caseload of missing children.

7 Conclusions and next steps

The identified information from the interviews as well as the research review should be included in the profiles of the children and thus reasonably can be incorporated into the algorithms. Applying the indicators to the case will enable a timelier recovery of the child. However, in order to increase the response time, the initial categorisation of the case and the resulting use of the indicators also has to be completed in a timely manner. The interviews conducted with different stakeholders in the field internationally have shown a great overlap in the information that was identified as crucial (cf. section 6.2).

Thus, in order to evaluate the behaviour of the missing child and to make sensible predictions on potential places of interest, the listed indicators should be analysed. Additionally, the lifestyle and hobbies that were not specifically identified for missing children cases might also be enlightening as missing children may have contacts through those and could be 'couch-hopping' there. Further, the norms and beliefs can have an influence on the behaviour of the child and their likeliness to seek help from official state actors, which thus should also be reflected in the input form of the ChildRescue platform. Two sets of data can be identified that are essential for the creation of the child's profile, namely the sociodemographic information on the children themselves and the information related to the circumstances of the case. The two sets of data that were identified by the analysis of the research, as well as the interviews as explained above, are displayed in the following table:

Socio-demographic information on child	Situational information on case
Full name	Financial status (carrying money, bank account)
Age	Timing (last day of school/date of deportation)
Gender	Place last seen
Appearance (height, weight)	Clothes worn on day of disappearance
Health status (pre-existing disease)	Emotional/mental state (substance abuse, suicidal tendencies)
Relationship status	Access to dating apps/ social media platforms
Police warrants	Hobbies/interests
Key contact persons/access to other persons	Family structures/ issues

It should be noted that the static nature of the socio-demographic data is limited. The relationship status as well as key contact persons can obviously change over time. However, even data such as the age and the name, can be altered in order to avoid detection. This is especially relevant in cases of unaccompanied minor migrants who ran away from their shelters. Thus, the additional use of photos is highly recommended if available. In turn, situational factors such as problematic family structures or hobbies can turn into more static characteristics over time. Yet, since it is possible to change them situationally, they were categorised as situational information that relate to specific cases, because they may not always be applicable. In order to gain the information needed for the creation of the profiles, friends and family as well as available social workers or other professional

actors, such as psychologists or police officers, who have been in touch with the child should be interviewed and the publicly available information of their social media profiles should be analysed.

As the data that is needed to create informative profiles of the children's situation and their activity or behavioural patterns is highly sensitive in nature (i.e. family issues, health status, personal data etc.), ChildRescue will take strict safekeeping measures to minimise the risk of breaching the data security. The safekeeping mechanisms of ChildRescue will be discussed further in D2.3, which deals specifically with the privacy and anonymization of the data. The results from D2.1, specifically the indicators identified as crucial for the creation of the children's profiles will be utilised as a base for D2.2 as well as D2.3, as they will inform the choice of algorithms and are essential for the design of the predictive analytics.

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Annex II: List of Abbreviations used

AT = Activity Theory
BKA = Bundeskriminalamt (German Federal Police)
CF = Child Focus
CTA = Central Tracing Agency
DJI = Deutsches Jugend Institut (German Youth Institute)
DL = Deep Learning
EU = European Union
FBI = Federal Bureau of Investigation (US)
FL or RFL = Family Links
GBV = Gender-based violence
ICRC = International Committee of the Red Cross
IOM = International Organisation of Migration
IRC = International Red Cross
MCE = Missing Children Europe
MFC = Multifunctional Center
ML = Machine Learning
NGO = Non-governmental organisation
NLP = Natural Language Processing
NS = National Societies
NSARDA = National Search and Rescue Dog Association UK
RC = Red Cross
RC/RC = Red Cross Red Crescent
SFE = Secure File Exchange
SOC = Smile of the Child
SNA = Social Network Analysis
TTF UAM = Trace the Face Unaccompanied Minors
TR = Tracing request
UAM = Unaccompanied minor migrant
UK = United Kingdom
US = United States of America
Vermi/utot = Vermisst/unidentifiziert tot (missing/ unidentified deceased taskforce at the BKA)